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[Basheer Wasef Fawzi Shaheen]

DOCTORAL DISSERTATION
DOKTORI ÉRTEKEZÉS

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DOCTORAL DISSERTATION
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DOCTORAL DISSERTATION

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Machine learning-based fault prognostics of mechanical components for Industry 4.0 maintenance support

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A dissertation

submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of

Doctor of Philosophy

Budapest, 2023

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NOMENCLATURE

ABBREVIATIONS

AI	Artificial intelligence	LL	Log-Likelihood
ACN	Arbitrarily connected network	LM	Levenberg–Marquardt
ANN	Artificial neural network	LSE	Least squared error
AR	Augmented reality	LSS	Low-speed shaft
BD	Big data	LSTM	Long short-term memory
BMLP	Bridged multi-layer perceptron	MC	Monte Carlo
BPM	Business process management	MES	Manufacturing execution system
BTA	Boosting tree algorithm	ML	Machine learning
CART	Classification and Regression Tree	MLE	Maximum likelihood estimation
CBM	Condition-based maintenance	MLP	Multi-layer perceptron
CDF	Cumulative distribution function	MLPL	Multi-layer perceptron with linear neurons
CI	Condition indicator	MMS	Maintenance management system
CM	Corrective maintenance	MoM	Method of moment
CMO	Condition monitoring	MTTR	Mean time to repair
CMMS	Computerised maintenance management system	NBN	Neuron-by-neuron
CMS	Condition monitoring system	NN	Neural network
CNC	Computerised numeric control	OM	Opportunistic maintenance
CNN	Convolutional neural network	PCA	Principal component analysis
CPPS	Cyber-physical production system	PDF	Probability density function
CPS	Cyber physical system	PdM	Predictive maintenance
CUSUM	Cumulative summation	PHM	Prognostic and health management
DCS	Distributed control system	PLC	Programmable logic controller
DDFF	Double dynamic forgetting factors	PM	Preventive maintenance
DL	Deep learning	PMF	Probability mass function
DOS-ELM	Denosing Online Sequential Extreme Learning Machine	R	Reliability
DT	Decision tree	RAMS	Reliability, Availability, Maintainability and Safety
EBP	Error back propagation	RBF	Radial basis function
EMS	Energy management system	RBM	Risk-based maintenance
ERP	Enterprise resources planning	RCM	Reliability centred maintenance
FCN	Fully connected network	RF	Random forest
FFM	Fully non-linear failure forecast method	RMSE	Root mean squared error
FNN	Fuzzy neural network	RNN	Recurrent neural network
GA	Genetic algorithm	RUL	Remaining useful life
GD	Gradient descent	SCADA	Supervisory control and data acquisition
HI	Health indicator	SPMF	Smart prescriptive maintenance framework
HSS	High-speed shaft	SSE	Sum squared error
ICT	Information, computer and telecommunication	SVM	Support vector machine
IIoT	Industrial internet of things	SVR	Support vector regression
IoT	Internet of things	USS	Updated selection strategy
LCC	Life cycle costs	VR	Virtual reality
		WT	Wind turbine

GREEK SYMBOLS, SUPERSCRIPTS, AND SUBSCRIPTS

m_{lin}	Linear function	J^T	Transposed Jacobian matrix
m_{bip}	Bipolar hyperbolic tangent (tanh) function	\mathbf{w}^*	New weights vector
α	Shape factor	P_{fail}	Failure probability
β	Scale factor	L	Likelihood
θ	Distribution parameters vector	H_k^{-1}	The approximate inverse update of the Hessian matrix
R^+	Positive codomain	\mathbf{s}_k	Step size
$f_j(\cdot)$	Activation function of neuron j	α_k	Position step length
Sum	Summation	\mathbf{p}_k	Search direction vector
R^2	Coefficient of determination	$\nabla\Lambda(\mathbf{w}_k)$	The gradient of the objective function
y	Output	$D_{(t)}$	Degradation path factor
x	Input	h	Predefined failure threshold
p	Input pattern	RUL_e	Expected remaining useful life
w	Weight	RUL_{ANN}	Predicted remaining useful life by the ANN model
b	Bias	ft	Failure time (point)
c	Constant	ft_e	Expected failure time
Gain & der	Activation function parameters	ft_{ANN}	Predicted failure time by the ANN model
j	Neuron index	$v(t)$	Gamma process
i	Input node index	$m(t)$	Mean degradation of a mechanical component
o_m	m^{th} network output	μ	Mean
ϵ	Error vector	σ	Variance
φ	Learning constant	σ^2	Standard deviation
y_i	Actual data	IW	Weights between inputs and hidden layers
\hat{y}_i	Estimated / predicted data	LW	Weights between hidden layers and outputs
\bar{y}	Data average	\mathbf{b}_1	Inputs and hidden layers biases vector
x'	Normalised data	\mathbf{b}_2	Hidden layers and outputs biases
np	Number of input patterns	$s(i)$	Log-likelihood ratio
no	Number of network outputs	$g(k)$	Recursive CUSUM
Q	The quasi-Hessian matrix	r	Power residual
\mathbf{g}	Gradient vector	k_a	Stopping / alarm time
J	Jacobian matrix	\hat{k}_0	Change occurrence time
$\boldsymbol{\eta}$	Gradient sub-vector	D	Delay time
θ	The quasi-Hessian sub-matrix	Λ	Negative log-likelihood
δ	Signal gain		
I	The identity matrix		
η	Combination coefficient		
$\overline{IY(j)}$	Number of internal inputs of the j^{th} neuron		
$\overline{IX(j)}$	Number of external inputs of the j^{th} neuron		
$Yp(j, i)$	Position of weight of the i^{th} internal input of the j^{th} neuron		
$Xp(j, i)$	Position of weight of the i^{th} external input of the j^{th} neuron		
$Bp(j)$	Position of the bias weight of the j^{th} neuron		

ABSTRACT

It is necessary to develop advanced fault prognostics techniques for improving maintenance planning and scheduling, productivity and enhancing the system's reliability, and avoiding unexpected shutdowns and the associated additional expenses. Such techniques include advanced failure prediction and remaining useful life (RUL) estimation of mechanical components comprising mechanical systems with complicated structures. The prediction algorithms must be accurate to support the decision-making in maintenance and implement the required corrections; otherwise, it would be difficult to detect any system anomalies and make the appropriate decisions properly.

Such advanced fault prognostic techniques are required to enhance the technical efficiency of the maintenance system in an Industry 4.0 workplace, and to develop advanced predictive maintenance (PdM) strategy which considered one of the main enablers of Industry 4.0 technologies.

The implementation of the PdM strategy requires other assisting tools such as enterprise resources planning (ERP), supervisory control and data acquisition system (SCADA), computerised maintenance management system (CMMS), sensors, and real-time condition monitoring systems, supported by the necessary software and graphical user interface (GUIs) units to facilitate the monitoring and assist maintenance experts in speeding up the decision-making process.

This dissertation presents diagnostics and prognostics methods for mechanical components based on their life degradation data. The fault prognostics are based on the component's failure prediction, remaining useful life (RUL) estimation, reliability and life degradation probability estimation. The prognostics models were developed based on different supervised machine learning (ML) techniques, mainly artificial neural networks (ANNs), including various training algorithms, network architectures, activation functions and computation methods. The proposed models require prior knowledge of the mechanical system and the analysed components, such as their general mechanism, inputs and outputs, for more effective modelling and accurate model design. The main assumption of the analysed data is that component degradation consists of multiple cycles of degradation along with a perfect maintenance replacement strategy. In terms of the fault prognostics method, the results showed its ability to predict real degradation data using NASA Ames milling dataset and achieved good results compared to a published similar study.

The neuron-by-neuron training algorithm (NBN) and the unique network architectures of fully connected networks (FCN) or arbitrarily connected networks (ACN) were used as the main components of the developed prognostic models due to

their high training capabilities for handling systems having complex structures. A special network design, an accumulative step in the network, was added to increase the models' ability to keep the monotonously increasing trend of the degradation process and to achieve highly accurate failure predictions and RUL estimations. The life degradation was estimated using a proposed probabilistic ANN model in which the maximum likelihood estimation method (MLE) was used to estimate the distribution parameters of each successive degradation point. The results show the high capability of the proposed model to predict successive degradation points, model the life degradation and estimate the distribution parameters of the predicted successive degradation points in the case of a perfect replacement strategy. Moreover, a method was developed using the prediction results to estimate the component's reliability over successive time slots and replacement cycles. The proposed method provides reasonable estimates and predictions compared to the theoretical calculations in the case of preventive maintenance (PM) optimisation in terms of reliability and availability estimation and PM cost minimisation.

The ANN-NBN model was applied to another industrial application: predicting the efficiency of a degraded wind turbine gearbox. A performance monitoring method was proposed to monitor the decreasing efficiency of a degraded gearbox based on the predicted power output and the predicted gearbox efficiency combined with the cumulative summation (CUSUM) change detection algorithm. The monitoring results showed a high degree of prediction and successful monitoring of the state change resulting from the decreased gearbox efficiency.

As the result of a comparative study of using different types of ML techniques for failure prognostics and degradation path prediction, the FCN and ACN network architectures combined with the NBN training algorithm confirmed its high prediction capability and high prediction success rate compared to other models.

The proposed methods were successfully tested and verified using several case studies from simulation datasets. The results were encouraging and showed that the proposed methods could be used as specialised diagnostics and prognostics methodologies and software tools that can efficiently predict the degradation process of mechanical components in different industrial applications.

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DEDICATION

*This dissertation is dedicated to the soul of my beloved late mother
and to my adorable wife, Shahd.*

For their endless love, support and encouragement.

Basheer Wasef Fawzi Shaheen

Chapter 1.

INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

1.1 Background

The changes occurring now on every side of our daily lives result from technological advancement. This advancement resulted in the emergence of new technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), Cloud Computing, Big Data, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Cyber-Physical Systems (CPS). These new technologies paved the way for new innovative opportunities and more significant development in socioeconomic life [1] and resulted in new intelligent manufacturing systems [2]. This new stage of technological development is often referred to as “Industry 4.0”.

Industry 4.0, or the 4th industrial revolution, was first introduced by the German government to maintain the effectiveness and efficiency of mass production [3]. Industry 4.0 was proposed to respond to an increasing market demand around the globe, which implies more challenges like intensified competition with leading industrial economies such as the United States and other developing economies such as China and India. In addition, Industry 4.0 came since many European countries are struggling to maintain their leading economic position while facing challenges such as ageing communities, resource limitations, demographic and social changes, and the dynamic nature of the world markets [2], [4]. Industrial development has gone through four major advancement stages. The first industrial revolution was initiated in the 18th century and was characterised by the mechanisation endorsed by the power generated by steam and water. The second one started at the beginning of the 20th century and was characterised by the utilisation of conveyor-based mass production supported by the emergence of electricity. The third revolution began in the 1960s and continued after, witnessing the deployment of the programable logic controller (PLC) and the integration of computerised systems in machines to elevate automation and mass production [3], [5], [6]. Furthermore, the fourth development stage, namely “Industry 4.0”, or the fourth industrial revolution occurring now, is characterised by the utilisation of new technologies [7], which results in new intelligent manufacturing systems [2].

Parallel to the development of the industry, maintenance management has continuously developed to cope with the new requirements of industrial revolutions [7], [8]. The origin of maintenance goes back to the first industrial revolution. During this period, maintenance was about using a machine until it failed and then repairing it. During the second industrial revolution, more complex machines were born, which

needed more care and more complex maintenance activities. This age was characterised by frequency-based maintenance [9]. After the second world war, in the 1950s, manufacturing sectors were rapidly grown with high competitiveness. Japanese engineers started to work on more proactive maintenance strategies to keep machines working and reduce downtimes; namely, a preventive maintenance strategy was applied. All technicians were encouraged to schedule general maintenance activities and report any other noted observations on the machine. This method succeeded in reducing downtimes but resulted in high costs. Lately, in the 1960s, more proactive maintenance strategies were developed, such as reliability-centred maintenance, risk-based maintenance, and total productive maintenance due to the development of new manufacturing technologies. During the 21st century, the complexity of manufacturing systems has increasing, and maintenance has become a crucial and integrated part of the overall production system, which demands more concentration on the reduction of the associated costs, as well as the increase of productivity, quality and profit. More complex knowledge is needed to achieve these goals. Thus, other maintenance strategies are being improved for better decision support systems, which leads to fewer machine failures and fewer downtimes.

1.1.1 Maintenance system

According to the European Committee of Standardization [10], maintenance management “includes all activities that determine the maintenance objectives, strategies, and responsibilities, and implementation by such means as maintenance planning, maintenance control, and the improvement of maintenance activities and economics”.

Maintenance was considered a nightmare in the past decades due to the application of corrective maintenance only [11]. During this process, the maintenance was mainly about repairing and replacing things when needed without planning, scheduling, or optimisation, combined with a lack of awareness of machine downtimes and behaviour. After that, maintenance became an independent function in most factories instead of a production sub-function [12]. With the inherent development of technology and industrial sectors, maintenance management has become a more complex function, including all technical and managerial skills and the flexibility to deal with dynamic business environments.

According to Duffuaa and Raouf [13], the maintenance management system consists of three major functions: planning, organising and control. As depicted in **Figure 1.1**, planning activities include strategic maintenance alliances in which the maintenance department should have its strategic maintenance plans in compliance with the strategic objectives of the company, such as outsourcing, organisation and

support. Moreover, planning includes maintenance load forecasting; its outputs are used as inputs for maintenance scheduling, maintenance control and maintenance capacity planning, in which the needed resources for maintenance activities are determined, including manpower, material, spare parts, tools and equipment. Furthermore, maintenance organisation planning is about planning the factors that affect the maintenance process, such as plant size, maintenance load, type of organisation and craftsmen skills. The last activity of maintenance planning is maintenance scheduling, in which the resources, including the workforce, are assigned to specific tasks within a timeframe.

Likewise, organising activities include designing jobs and tasks, standards, and project management for better control. Feedback and controlling represent the essential parts of the management to control work, material, and inventory, including spare parts, cost, quality and the overall performance of the manufacturing system.

Figure 1.1. Maintenance Management System – adopted from [13]

1.1.1.1 Maintenance strategies

Maintenance is not just about retaining and restoring a unit. It is certainly true that the selection of a suitable maintenance strategy plays a key role in the manufacturing processes and production planning and scheduling phases to reduce unscheduled shutdowns, enhance the productivity and the efficiency of the overall production system and finally, optimise the overall cost. The goal is to find the general optimum for any process based on predetermined requirements and targets.

Manufacturing systems consist of various types of machines and components, which rely on each other and are arranged in a specific and consequential way to achieve the overall production goals and produce the final product. **Figure 1.2** shows different mechanical components, such as gears and bearings, which are considered

critical components in the mechanical system. In mass and batch production systems, shutdowns of a production line, machine, or a failed component affect the overall production process and culminate in different types of losses, i.e., orders delay and increased set-up costs, and affect the overall productivity.

Figure 1.2. Samples of mechanical components

For this purpose, maintenance strategies need to be addressed and adequately selected. The most critical maintenance strategies of any modern manufacturing system are presented in Figure 1.3.

Figure 1.3. Main maintenance strategies

Corrective maintenance (CM): CM is also known as run-to-failure or breakdown maintenance. Its concept is based on fixing things after a failure occurrence [12]. It can be carried out promptly after the failure occurrence or postponed for further repair or replacement actions.

Preventive maintenance (PM): PM ensures the equipment does not break unexpectedly. To achieve this, maintenance must be performed regularly to maintain machine stability [14].

Risk-based maintenance (RBM): In RBM, the available resources for maintenance tasks are prioritised toward the machines or other assets that have the most significant threat to the whole system once they fail [15]. Maintenance plans and schedules are updated based on the associated risk analysis of the potentially failed asset, and then they are monitored through other maintenance strategies, such as condition-based maintenance [16], [17].

Condition-based maintenance (CBM): CBM is a maintenance action and decision-making program which recommends suitable actions according to the condition monitoring information by utilising the prognostic methods for more reliable and cost-effective maintenance [18].

Reliability Centred Maintenance (RCM): RCM is an approach originally developed for the aircraft industry and used to generate a cost-effective maintenance schedule by utilising the estimated parameters of the reliability of the system [19]. For applications that have safety issues, the minimisation of the costs and downtime, as the main goal, is usually done by eliminating the chance of failure occurrence by making a balance between safety and availability along with cost-effective maintenance. RCM has two categories: the first is to analyse and categorise the failure modes according to their effects on the systems, and the other is to assess the maintenance scheduled impacts on the system's reliability. The results are formalised in the methodology of the failure mode and effects analysis (FMEA).

Predictive Maintenance (PdM): PdM represents an optimised trade-off between maintenance and performance costs. In addition, it measures efficiency and productivity and predicts the remaining useful life before the failure happens; it includes health condition monitoring, the prognostics of the future system behaviour and helps in the decision-making process [20], [21]. It has been found that predictive maintenance is an effective strategy that can reduce the downtime of machines by 30-50% and extend their lifetime by 20-40% compared to traditional strategies [22], [23].

Prescriptive maintenance: An advanced version of predictive maintenance supported by further decision-making mechanisms. Prescriptive maintenance goes one step further than PdM; it inspects not only the equipment to be maintained but

also its environment and the correlation between them [24]. Furthermore, this strategy needs very complex knowledge that is aligned with software support, AI, complex sensory systems for instant condition-based monitoring, IoT, Big Data, Augmented Reality (AR), and other integration assisting tools in the total integration of maintenance management with Industry 4.0.

Opportunistic maintenance (OM): According to [25] and [26], OM is a systematic method of collecting, investigating and preplanning activities for the generation of maintenance tasks to act in the occurrence of an opportunity [27]. A typical example is when a complex machine is disassembled to replace a broken component, and it might be worth replacing other components that are close to their end-of-life.

The costs of the main maintenance strategies can be summarised in **Figure 1.4**.

Figure 1.4. Maintenance strategies costs

In preventive maintenance, the prevention cost is high, while the repair cost is low due to the limited number of failures that occur. In corrective maintenance, a larger number of faults occur; this leads to a high cost of repair and a low cost of prevention. Predictive maintenance (PdM) as an optimum strategy can improve the reliability, availability, and maintainability of the overall manufacturing system and reduce the total maintenance costs as a result.

Furthermore, condition monitoring systems (CMS), including performance monitoring, sometimes known as “health monitoring systems,” are widely used for diagnosing faults and monitoring the health of the components. CMS includes sensors, data acquisition, data processing, cabling, and other installations that provide continuous and real-time information on the monitored component condition [28], [29].

In condition-based maintenance (CBM) and predictive maintenance (PdM), condition monitoring systems play a crucial role in reducing the costs of occurred failures and enhancing the functionality of any system as they are being widely used as a tool for the detection of anomalies and failures by providing early warnings [30].

Supervisory control and data acquisition systems (SCADA) are one of the widely used data sources in CMS due to their cost-effectiveness and high reliability [31], [32], [33], [34].

According to Hameed et al. [35], a CMS has three main characteristics; (1) Early warnings that can help avoid sudden shutdowns and improve the planning and scheduling tasks. (2) Problem identification is useful to have general insights into the health of the system and provide the proper maintenance service at the right time. (3) Continuous monitoring of the different components and the whole system provides constant information indicating that the system is working correctly. These characteristics help minimise shutdowns and maintenance costs, prolong components' lifetime, and ensure quality control of the different processes.

1.1.1.2 Reliability analysis

Reliability is defined as the likelihood that a system will carry out its intended function under normal operating conditions for a specified period of time [36].

In reliability analysis, the maintenance experts are mainly interested in life span margins and the present reliability of the main mechanical components which comprise the manufacturing system [37]. Degradation means the reduction of components' performance, reliability and life span, which lead to failure once it exceeds a pre-defined threshold. Degradation measurements are considered one of the main factors determining the life span or the failure point of the mechanical components and providing information about the performance and precision during the operation [37]. Moreover, degradation measurements provide information to determine the time-varying characteristics of the component and show the relationship between the degradation path and the failures.

Probabilistic modelling of a failure law, its degradation path and the projected distributions is an efficient way to predict reliability and the life span of the mechanical components [38]. The monotonously increasing degradation path is presented in **Figure 1.5**.

Figure 1.5. Sample section of a degradation path

The condition of the component is probabilistically degrading over time, where at any point in time, there is a specific distribution of the degradation value. From **Figure 1.5**, it can be seen that as time increases, the variance of the degradation measurements becomes larger. Moreover, the degradation paths might deviate significantly from the mean, resulting in the distributions shown in **Figure 1.6**.

Reliability can be estimated as the likelihood that all the degradation measurements fall below a predefined threshold value until a given time instant. For some special applications, the degradation path can be monotonously decreasing; hence the reliability can be defined as the likelihood that the degradation measurement falls above a predefined threshold value. Common examples of degradation measurements are mechanical tool wear, degraded light intensity, degraded battery rechargeability, and crack propagation [39].

In the case of an unknown failure mechanism (degradation law) that characterizes the degradation path propagation, degradation modelling will not be feasible to estimate the reliability or the RUL of the components [38]. Instead of estimating the degradation path, the distribution of the time to failure can be used. The Weibull and Gamma distributions are considered as the most important distributions in reliability analysis and probabilistic diagnosis.

For failure time distributions, graphical and analytical methods are used to estimate the distribution parameters. The analytical estimations have lower estimation errors than the graphical ones; however, they need a larger number of iterations. The analytical methods include the maximum likelihood estimation (MLE), which is the most popular method, the least square estimation (LSE) and the method of moments

(MoM) [40]. **Figure 1.6** depicts the effect of distribution parameter variations on the shape of the distribution ideal histograms.

Figure 1.6. Gamma and Weibull PDFs - ideal histograms with variable shape factor values α and constant scale factor $\beta=3$

1.1.2 Industry 4.0

Industry 4.0 has been intensively discussed since the time it was first proposed by the German government in 2011 [2], [41]. However, a brief definition of Industry 4.0, including its features and technologies, is vital to justify the topic being discussed in this dissertation.

Industry 4.0 indicates the recent technological advancements and the integration of information and communication technology (ICT) applications in production systems [42]. This integration resulted in new production and management systems paradigms that depend mainly on higher communication and collaboration among the value chain [6]. Furthermore, the availability and affordability of sensors, networking and control devices, in addition to the supercomputing power and cloud computing, paved the way for the concept called cyber-physical system (CPS), where the whole system, including information, objects and humans, are interconnected [43], [44]. Industry 4.0 is also known for integrating IoT in the manufacturing shopfloor and the management supporting activities such as logistics and planning. Such integration resulted in a global network for the whole system, including machining, warehousing and customers, where each party can exchange information [4].

Industry 4.0 significantly impacts several aspects of production systems, i.e., optimising resource allocation and lowering human resources and logistics costs [45]. Moreover, Industry 4.0 has enhanced the flexibility of business processes by combining different business inputs, such as time, cost, quality, labour and logistics [4]. Overall, Industry 4.0 is the synergistic combination of several technologies,

resulting in several features that can be utilised in modern production systems and the whole value chain.

1.1.2.1 Industry 4.0 technologies

This section presents the most commonly studied Industry 4.0 technologies.

The Internet of Things (IoT) represents the system where elements in the material world, such as machines, equipment or devices, are communicating with each other and the cyber elements, such as software and data [1], [46]. The main characteristic of the IoT is a strongly decentralised and heterogeneous digital information exchange between devices connected in a network. IoT offers the possibility of instant response to any request from the surrounding objects or environments [47]. IoT enhanced production systems by optimising resources based on the collected data from different locations in the value chain. Such information includes production monitoring, quality inspection, consumption information and product performance under different operational conditions [32].

Cloud Computing comprises online resources such as servers, applications and networks to offer regular services that require higher investment and resources to operate locally. Cloud computing is being highly used nowadays for its efficiency, cost-effectiveness, stability and high-power availability if needed [50]. Moreover, cloud computing is one of the main infrastructures of Big Data.

Big Data is related to the development of the internet and connectivity that generated production-related data at large volume, velocity, variety and veracity. Big Data means not only the data but also the data processing. The collected data require more sophisticated systems that can handle, analyse and transform the data into useful knowledge. Data coming from the devices of the IoT is being analysed, only meaningful information is extracted, and knowledge is transferred efficiently to support business activities [1].

Simulation has become an essential tool in the industry 4.0 context. It is a powerful computational tool for designing, analysing and understanding the behaviour of complex systems; it plays a crucial role in the successful implementation of digital manufacturing [51], [52]. Moreover, complex systems can be modelled with simulation, and virtual experiments can be conducted to validate or configure processes or products to support decision-making [34]. Deep insights into such complex systems can be obtained through different simulation techniques, whereas the digital twin creation helps analyse the real-time data to predict failures and breakdowns and improve the maintenance planning and scheduling activities [53].

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is considered one of the primary keys to transforming manufacturing systems in the era of Industry 4.0. Through integrating IoT, Cloud

Computing, Big Data and AI tools, manufacturing systems can make actual decisions by accurately monitoring and analysing their processes through real communication modules to coordinate and monitor all activities between machines, people, sensors and other parts of the production system [54]. Meanwhile, machine learning (ML) techniques are used in real-life scenarios to predict the future behaviour of the system. The most suitable algorithm can be chosen based on the given computational power, memory resources, and the amount and quality of the data to be analysed [55]. Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) [56], Neuro-Fuzzy systems [57], [58], Hidden Markov Models in Bayesian methods [59], [60], Kalman Filter, Particle Filter and variants [61], Logistic Regression [62] algorithms and many other tools are used to develop effective machine learning models to achieve better operational maintenance and business excellence.

Cyber-Physical Systems (CPSs) comprise the environment in which the physical world, including machines, warehousing and the whole manufacturing system, is transformed into the cyber world through network devices [3], where both the cyber and the physical parts interact. The exhaustive connectivity, supported by the supercomputing power, has enabled such a system to gather and process real-time data and control production processes instantly. In an Industry 4.0-enabled facility, every process is simulated and verified virtually, and once an optimum plan is ready, it is directly transformed into the physical world [63]. Such technology has automatically enabled production systems to adapt to instant production changes [5]. The vision of future factories (smart factories) can be achieved through Industry 4.0, in which the CPS monitors the physical processes and visualises the real world by making virtual copies of these processes to implement and make decentralised decisions and actions [64]. A new type of smart production system known as a Cyber-Physical Production System (CPPS) is emerged due to the development of new Industry 4.0 applications in smart factories [65]. Moreover, as stated by Monostori [66], CPPS is a more specific application of CPS in manufacturing [67], [68]. It refers to integrating computer sciences, information and communication technologies, and manufacturing science and technologies.

1.1.2.2 Industry 4.0 features

Ibarra et al. [43] highlighted the major features of Industry 4.0 as the following:

Integration is the process of combining all elements of the production system, including machines, products and control systems using sensors and actuators, and connecting these elements with other key players such as customers, suppliers, logistics, transportation, maintenance and production management [45]. Henning et al. [4] highlighted three types of integration: horizontal, vertical and end-to-end.

Vertical integration refers to the integration of different units within the intelligent factory, while horizontal integration refers to the integration between the factories of the whole manufacturing value chain. End-to-end integration means the inherent integration in the entire value chain supporting the processes of different stages of the product's lifecycle, such as product design, production planning, production execution, maintenance and recycling [69], [70].

Interconnection refers to the interconnection between different elements in the value chain. An example is an interconnection between machines that handle similar work to coordinate the flow of products and avoid downtime or production delays. The product can inform the machine about the kind of operation to do. Such interconnection elevates intelligent production. Likewise, products are smart and connected; once a product is produced in a machine, the next machine is well-informed jointly with the conveyor or the logistics robot responsible for transporting the product to the next production process [63]. Moreover, the connection between products, machines and processes through data exchange points results in more flexibility and autonomy. Such a process is realised by integrating the elements of cyber-physical systems and results in an intelligent value chain that can adapt, diagnose and repair itself remotely [71].

Interoperability is a crucial feature in Industry 4.0; it is the ability of two different systems to communicate with each other and to use the functionality of each other according to basic and common technological standards [5]. Therefore, machines, products, suppliers and customers are integrated through a common language. Interoperability is vital for the effective operation of IoT, as every machine should have an interoperability standard that makes communication with other machines possible [46].

Decentralisation is the capability of a smart product, machine or CPS to identify and successfully connect itself to another physically decentralised system and provide information about its state or conditions; thus, decentralisation could be either physical or logical [72].

1.2 Research context, research scope and objectives

1.2.1 Predictive maintenance and Industry 4.0 – The research context

Manufacturing and many other industries are currently attempting to meet the the fourth industrial revolution requirements, which aims to integrate cyber and physical production systems as well as maintenance activities using a variety of technologies, such as cyber-physical systems (CPS), internet of things (IoT), artificial intelligence (AI), cloud computing, big data and others to create smart and independent production systems. Such integration results in a huge amount of related data and the need to implement intelligent maintenance, including advanced prognostic and health management (PHM) techniques such as condition-based maintenance (CBM) and predictive maintenance (PdM). As a result, numerous related study areas have examined new trends and breakthroughs in maintenance planning and scheduling and decision support, utilising various data types and AI solutions. [73], [74], [75]. PHM includes different maintenance analysis techniques, such as condition monitoring (CMO), fault diagnostics and prognostics, fault detection and maintenance decision support. **Figure 1.7** shows the motivation and the context of the research work conducted in this dissertation.

Due to the rigorous operating conditions and the associated equipment deterioration over time, unanticipated failures may cause serious problems, such as machine breakdowns, unexpected shutdowns, dramatic reduction of machine availability and consequent production interruptions. Failures or degraded components increase maintenance costs, accounting for up to 70% of the overall costs [76]. To avoid such scenarios, maintenance resources must be well-planned in advance [77].

One of the most challenging aspects of fault prognostics of mechanical components is the development of advanced RUL prediction models utilising various types of AI, especially machine learning (ML) techniques. The work presented in this dissertation aims to develop and provide a novel data-driven fault prognostics model to estimate the remaining useful life (RUL) of mechanical components, which can also assist in implementing PdM and reducing the effects of unexpected failures of manufacturing systems.

A more specific aim of the research has been to build a specialised ML-based prediction methodology and software tool that can efficiently predict the degradation processes. A further motivation is to integrate the developed prediction software tool into an existing maintenance planning and scheduling platform to predict failures and perform discrete event simulations of maintenance events more robustly.

Figure 1.7. Predictive maintenance and Industry 4.0 – The research context

1.2.2 Research scope and objectives

The main scope of the research presented in this dissertation is to develop new methods and algorithms for more effective maintenance solutions of mechanical components and manufacturing equipment utilising various types of data analysis and AI techniques.

Such methods assist to

- Increase the availability and reliability of the machines and the manufacturing systems;
- Reduce the maintenance-related life cycle cost (LCC);
- Improve maintenance plans and schedules;
- Improve the productivity and efficiency of the overall production system.

This can be achieved by utilising such techniques to predict the potential failures, estimate the components' RUL, simulate the effects of the selected maintenance strategies and schedules, and finally optimise the most influential factors of the system, such as the LCCs and the availability of the machine, as presented in **Figure 1.7**.

The following specific objectives were accomplished through this dissertation.

- Introducing an ML-based method that can model complex structures of arbitrarily failed machines / mechanical components using unique artificial neural network (ANN) architectures.
- Developing a novel data-driven fault prognostics model to estimate the RUL of a mechanical component, which can assist in implementing a PdM-based Industry 4.0 strategy and reducing the effects of unexpected failures of manufacturing systems.
- Building a specialised ANN-based prediction methodology and software tool that can efficiently predict the degradation processes.
- Developing an ANN-based methodology to predict stochastic failure times that can be used to generate failure events within Monte-Carlo simulations in a maintenance planning and scheduling environment.
- Analysing the effectiveness of the developed model by comparing it with other data-driven prediction models, as well as evaluating the effects of changing key parameters of the developed model on the performance.
- Investigating the applicability of the ANN-NBN model of diagnosing and performance monitoring of other mechanical components such as the gearbox of a wind turbine.

1.3 Outline of the dissertation

The dissertation is composed of eight chapters as the following.

- Chapter 1: Introduction and literature review. Introducing a brief background, context and scope of the research area and objectives. In addition, an overview of the latest related literature to the topics covered in the dissertation, including maintenance management system functions, Industry 4.0 and ML techniques used to improve maintenance activities. Main key findings, research gaps, and future opportunities are discussed and summarised.
- Chapter 2: Methods, data and analysis tools. An overview of the ML categories, models, training algorithms, activation functions, network architectures and computational methods. The used neuron-by-neuron (NBN) training method is also discussed in detail. Overview of the used feature selection and importance analysis methods of the models' predictors along with the used performance metrics to evaluate the developed models and compare them. Moreover, the datasets used for training, testing and verifying the developed models are described along with the data collection method (simulation) and data preparation. Moreover, general descriptions of the datasets, analysis software and tools are included in this chapter.
- Chapters 3, 4, 5 and 6: Presenting, analysing and discussing the research results and novelty. The new scientific contributions are also highlighted.
- Chapter 7: Conclusions and future work. Summarising the key findings and main insights of the research works conducted in this dissertation and the potential future opportunities.
- Chapter 8: Main scientific contribution and related publications. Summarising the new scientific contribution of the research works addressed in Chapters 3, 4, 5, and 6 as five theses, along with their list of corresponding publications.

1.4 LITERATURE REVIEW

1.4.1 Maintenance in the context of Industry 4.0

Industry 4.0 is the umbrella of several newly developed technologies such as IoT, Cloud Computing, Big Data, simulation, AI and CPS. The adaptation of Industry 4.0 is vital at many managerial levels in manufacturing systems. To cope with this, an implementation strategy is needed for digitalising the manufacturing systems and their support systems, such as maintenance planning and scheduling. This can be achieved by successfully integrating the new ICT technologies and Big Data capabilities through the CPS, which can lead to the ability to improve maintenance significantly through the manufacturing system.

The transformation from the current maintenance status to digital maintenance complying with Industry 4.0 requirements needs recommendations and instructions to be generated, as in Fusko et al. [78]. Moving forward to digital and smart factories, the following industry 4.0 factors present the main triggers of such transformation: real-time data collection through sensory or condition monitoring systems, data processing methods to ensure the accuracy and quality of the collected data, and finally, prediction models to prevent failures and update information. Smart and predictive maintenance are the main concepts used in smart factories [79], where many production and maintenance tasks need to be managed simultaneously, such as data collection and evaluation, resource availability, production, maintenance and quality control. To increase the production processes' effectiveness in terms of maintenance, reduce the required workforce and increase the effectiveness of the management and planning process, Total Productive Maintenance (TPM) practices were digitalised by Tortorella et al. [80] deriving five case-based research prepositions. Similarly, an innovative approach to managing the maintenance process of complex equipment in a production hall within preventive maintenance and TPM concepts was developed by Hardt et al. [81]. This approach focuses on gathering and analysing the operational data of different equipment components working under different users and operational conditions.

Table 1.1 classifies some selected articles according to the maintenance concepts, Industry 4.0 technologies and integration assisting tools in order to link each maintenance concept such as PdM with the potential Industry 4.0 technology along with the used integration assisting tools.

Table 1.1. Literature classification results

Article	Maintenance concept	Industry 4.0 technology	Integration assisting tools / data acquisition
[82]	PdM	AI-ML	Sensory – CMS
[83]	Combined PdM	CPS & AI-ML	Sensory – CMS
[84]	Intelligent PdM	AI-ML	Sensory – Real-time CMS
[85]	Intelligent PdM	CPS, AI-ML, Cloud computing & IoT	Sensory – Real-time CMS
[86]	Low-costs PdM	AI-ML & CPS	Sensory – Real-time CMS
[87]	PdM	AI-ML	SCADA & GUI
[88]	PdM	AI-ML	SCADA & CMMS
[89]	Low-costs PdM	AI-ML	ERP, DCS & MES
[90]	PdM	AI-ML	Sensory – CMS
[91]	PdM 4.0	AI-ML & CPS	Sensory – CMS
[92]	Low-costs PdM	AI-ML	Sensory – CMS
[93]	PdM 4.0	AI-ML, Big Data & CPS	Sensory – CMS
[94]	PdM	AI-ML	Real-time CMS
[75]	PdM	AI-ML	Sensory system & Microsoft Azure
[95]	PdM	AI-ML & Big Data	Sensory – CMS
[96]	PdM	AI-ML	Sensory – CMS
[97]	PdM	AI-ML	Sensory – CMS
[98]	PdM	Big Data & AI-ML	Sensory – CMS
[99]	PdM	Big Data & AI-ML	Sensory – CMS
[100]	Smart PdM	AI-ML	Real-time CMS
[101]	Intelligent maintenance	AI-ML, IoT & Big Data	Real-time CMS, CMMS & ERP
[102]	Intelligent PdM	AI-ML, Simulation & Cloud computing	Sensory – CMS
[103]	PdM	AI-ML, Big Data & IIoT	Real-time CMS
[104]	PdM	AI-ML	Real-time CMS
[105]	Intelligent maintenance	AI-ML	Real-time CMS
[106]	Maintenance 4.0	-	ERP & CMMS
[107]	Maintenance 4.0	-	ERP & CMMS
[108]	Maintenance 4.0	Simulation	ERP & CMMS
[109]	PdM	CPS	Real-time CMS
[110]	PdM	IoT	Real-time CMS
[111]	PdM	AI-ML & Digital twin	Real-time CMS
[112]	PdM	AI-ML	Sensory – CMS

1.4.1.1 Predictive maintenance

Based on the Industry 4.0 features and technologies and the intensive literature review conducted in this dissertation, the latest maintenance trends and terms have been investigated. These new trends are based on the key role of predictive maintenance (PdM) as the main integration enabler.

The predictive maintenance approach is the focal point of recent AI applications in the context of Industry 4.0. ML algorithms help detect and predict the failures before their occurrence to avoid unplanned shutdowns and predict the equipment's remaining useful life (RUL) [113], [114], [115],[116], [117], [118]

Machine learning methods also support the scheduling of maintenance activities through combined IoT technology to reduce downtime and maintenance costs and increase machine availability [82], [109], [110], [119], [120]. PdM can also be implemented using digital twins [111].

Kiangala and Wang [87] designed an experimental method to detect conveyor motor faults and generate a predictive maintenance schedule accordingly. Real-time vibration data are collected from SCADA systems connected to a graphical user interface (GUI) to display the predictive maintenance schedule. This leads to an easy reconfiguration of the maintenance rules when needed. Additionally, historical records and the number of previous breakdowns can be obtained from the computerised maintenance management system (CMMS) for future planning and to evaluate the applied reconfigurations [88].

To connect the predictive maintenance concept with Industry 4.0 technologies, Li et al. [90] introduced a framework of predictive maintenance to analyse and predict faults in a machining centre. The framework included data acquisition, data pre-processing, fault diagnosis and prognosis based on ANN, performance analysis and maintenance schedule optimisation. Similarly, Tran Anh et al. [96] presented a PdM strategy applied in an automotive manufacturing company to cope with Industry 4.0 requirements focusing on its impact on maintenance optimisation and financial situation.

ML algorithms and data-driven modelling are widely used for failure prediction [112], [121], [122], [123].

A PdM model using an ML technique (Bayesian Filter) was developed by Ruiz-Sarmiento et al. [94] to predict the gradual degradation of machinery in a rolling process and then apply maintenance actions. Likewise, Paolanti et al. [75] used the Random Forest approach for PdM. The required data were collected from the sensory system and machine's PLC, while the communication protocols were set using Microsoft Azure. The results show that the developed PdM predicted the machine statuses efficiently and accurately. Kiangala and Wang [97] suggested an experimental design of a PdM framework to detect the deterioration in conveyor motors in small manufacturing firms. To classify the abnormalities into production threatening or not, an ML classification model was built using time-series imaging and a convolutional neural network (CNN) to increase the classification accuracy combined with

parameterised rectifier linear unit to improve the performance of the model. Moreover, principal component analysis (PCA) was applied to the multivariate time series to reduce their dimensions to two channels. The experimental results showed that this PdM framework is better in performance and accuracy than the traditional approaches.

In the same way, a prediction model to predict the anomalies of the bearing of an assembly conveyor carrier using Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) devices, ANN and sound analysis was developed by Tanuska et al. [103]. This model is based on an online condition monitoring system consisting of data collection and processing, data storage and anomaly detection to provide early warnings. These processes aim at detecting the failure of the wheel bearing that leads to stuck stopping the movement of the carrier and shutting down the whole conveyor. Moreover, the detection process aims to minimise the unscheduled shutdowns of the conveyor and prepare proper schedules for maintenance. Fernandes et al. [104] implemented a mixed CBM/PdM approach in an automotive case study by introducing the Business Process Management (BPM) and the Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) methods to decrease maintenance costs and improve productivity. The implemented methods resulted in better prediction of the breakdowns of the machines, better scheduling for maintenance and components replacement, minimisation of the periodic inspection of the machines, and finally, minimisation of the number of unplanned shutdowns and emergency stops.

In terms of the effective use of PdM, Sahal et al. [99] filled the technological integration gaps between Industry 4.0 applications and existing open-source Big Data and streaming analytics technologies in the railway transportation and wind energy industries by showing the requirements of implementing PdM and the available Big Data technologies that could serve these requirements as one of the main Industry 4.0 technologies. This study resulted in guidelines and technology combinations of open-source tools that could help implement PdM and support the decision-makers.

PdM is considered the central concept of integration; different concepts connected to PdM were found in the literature. Ferreira et al. [83] utilised PdM in sheet metal working machinery to achieve a full proactive maintenance system where three approaches are employed; (1) component failure detection using various detection means and models; (2) component failure prediction depending on the collected data from the sensory system and then to predict the RUL of the machine or the component as well as the potential failures before their occurrence; (3) and the last approach focuses on component failure diagnosis to identify the root causes of the problems. These approaches utilise empirical models to help technicians to diagnose the

problem. Pilot implementation of the framework was realised, and the result was a CPS integrated with the maintenance system (Combined predictive and proactive maintenance).

Similarly, smart or intelligent maintenance strategies based on the concept of PdM are used by some researchers. On the plant level, Chiu et al. [85] proposed a predictive maintenance system based on Industry 4.0 technologies to overcome the problem resulting from the fact that PdM is usually designed for single equipment where the resources allocation might be complicated when there are tens or hundreds of equipment in the factory level. The proposed PdM system is based on modified Industry 4.0 tools, namely “cyber-physical agent and advanced manufacturing cloud of things”. Moreira et al. [100] upgraded an injection moulding machine in an Industry 4.0 environment with real-time monitoring sensors to reduce the number of unnecessary shutdowns and failures, decrease maintenance costs and maximise the performance of the machine. Moreover, the collected data enables the implementation of smart predictive maintenance, solving the main key challenge of Industry 4.0.

In the same way, Nordal and El-Thalji [101] proposed an intelligent maintenance management system in compliance with Industry 4.0 requirements. The developed intelligent system included (1) analysis, evaluation and needs identification of the existing maintenance system, (2) extraction of the requirements of the future system, including the business model and the related stakeholders and industry 4.0 requirements, and (3), finally, modelling the desired future system. Communication in all maintenance management levels was clarified, including asset-to-asset, asset-to-enterprise, and enterprise-to-enterprise communication, supported by advanced technologies for computation, such as predictive maintenance, machine learning and maintenance optimisation. Maintenance operations were managed using an appropriate integrated ERP and CMMS.

In terms of assets management as a central part of the maintenance management system, Toeh et al. [102] presented an integrated predictive maintenance-based machine learning model in fog computing to manage the assets (physical, virtual and human resources) using a genetic algorithm (GA). Fog Workflowsim was used to simulate time and costs and to evaluate the performance of the GA along with other methods such as MinMin and MaxMin. Logistic regression as a supervised machine learning algorithm was used to build the predictive maintenance model that reached 95.1% training and prediction accuracy.

“PdM4.0” is a new concept defined by researchers using different approaches to implementing PdM in an Industry 4.0 environment. Sahba et al. [91] proposed a novel PdM framework based on the advanced Reference Architecture Model Industry

4.0 (RAMI 4.0) that aims at reducing the maintenance and operation associated cost of a broadcasting chain. RAMI 4.0 is a model demonstrating features of the technical assets and the concepts of Industry 4.0. The proposed framework succeeded in increasing the stability of the broadcasting system and decreasing maintenance costs. Likewise, RAMI 4.0 architecture was used by Sang et al. [93] to support the PdM strategy in Industry 4.0 environment using a unique framework called FIWARE for data exchange between various organisations and considering security requirements. This integrated PdM model provided an effective method for optimising the processes and monitoring the equipment conditions using different machine learning models and Big Data technologies.

In terms of reducing associate maintenance costs, various studies focused on developing low-cost PdM models. Sezer et al. [86] developed an Industry 4.0 (CPS) architecture for low-cost predictive maintenance for small and medium manufacturing enterprises. In the developed CPS architecture, the temperature and vibration variables of a CNC machining process were measured. Accordingly, a regression tree model was used to predict the quality of the machined parts and then to reject or accept them based on the quality threshold and the correlation between temperature, vibration and roughness. Furthermore, Alarcón et al. [89] presented a low-cost integration model of Energy Management Systems (EMS) and Maintenance Management Systems (MMS) in a manufacturing firm. Several technologies and tools that support working in an Industry 4.0 environment were used in the model, such as ERP, Distributed Control Systems (DCS) or Manufacturing Execution Systems (MES) to collect, analyse, control, detect the failure and monitor the conditions of the available machinery including their consumed electrical energy. Results show a significant reduction in energy consumption, the number of required maintenance events and the time of component replacements. Likewise, for small and medium manufacturing enterprises, Adu-Amankwa et al. [92] proposed a cost-effective PdM architecture for a CNC machine, which could reduce maintenance costs.

For wind energy applications, many research works used SCADA data to construct CMS of different wind turbine (WT) components, as in [124], [125], [126], [127], [128],[129], [130], [131],[132], [133]. The real-time condition of a WT component can be indicated through the measured operational data acquired from the SCADA system, such as temperature, wind speed and the generated power, which can be analysed to derive relationships between these operational data and then the condition of the WT can be determined using various techniques [134], [34]. García et al. [135] reported several condition monitoring (CMO) techniques that can be used to monitor the conditions of different WT components, such as vibration analysis,

acoustic emission, ultrasonic testing, oil analysis, strain measurements and process parameter and performance monitoring in which the relationships between different parameters, such as wind speed and generated power can be employed to monitor the WT condition through early detection of the associated faults or anomalies.

Different tools and methods were used to monitor the process performance. Cui et al. [136] used control charts to monitor the shift in lubricant pressure by detecting the causing anomalies, while Long et al. [133] used them to monitor the performance of the generated power by analysing different power curve profiles. Similarly, Wang et al. [137] monitored the residuals of oil temperature to detect gearbox failures. A machine learning (ML) technique was used by Hsu et al. [138] to monitor and diagnose different faults of a WT to develop a PdM strategy assisting in planning maintenance needs. Likewise, Wang et al. [139] used a ML technique to monitor and detect bearing faults using SCADA data; this method was able to assess the general status of the WT with high accuracy. For the same purposes, Dao [130] developed a model to monitor the WT performance based on real SCADA data by detecting abnormal issues resulting from the changing temperature of the generator. For process monitoring and fault detection, Borchersen and Kinnaert [140] developed a fault detection and monitoring model for the cooling system of a WT generator. The cumulative summation (CUSUM) change detection algorithm was used to evaluate and monitor the temperature residuals.

1.4.1.2 Maintenance 4.0

Recent studies investigated the term “Maintenance 4.0” which indicates the latest trends of maintenance management to meet the integration requirements of Industry 4.0 and the sustainable development aspects [106]. It was found that the term Maintenance 4.0 comprises the use of advanced analytics methods not only to predict failure (predictive maintenance) but also to avoid such failures and optimise maintenance schedules and resources (prescriptive maintenance). In other words, Kumar and Galar [107] stated that Maintenance 4.0 uses advanced technologies to perform predictive analytics and generate solutions by integrating maintenance practices that deal with data collection, processing, analysis, visualisation, decision-making and Industry 4.0 technologies and features. On the other hand, Maintenance 4.0 enables the effective use of ICT platforms such as ERP and CMMS to manage the whole maintenance management system at all levels [141]. Smart and sustainable maintenance is the key element of Maintenance 4.0, where the integration of digital technologies enables instant access to the required detailed real-time information and manages the assets’ life cycle [142]. Similarly, Giacotto et al. [108] discussed two related terms in the context of the integration process of Industry 4.0. They defined

“Maintenance 4.0” as a smart or intelligent maintenance framework along with its technological enablers, while “Ecosystem 4.0”, also associated with Maintenance 4.0, refers to a situation where the applied maintenance technologies for different machines are supported by and in harmony with the production system; meanwhile, the Ecosystem 4.0 facilitates the integration process between machines and their operators in an Industry 4.0 environment. In a case study of an aircraft assembly line, Giacotto et al. [108] designed and tested a framework-based Ecosystem 4.0 and maintenance activities integration using the Smart Prescriptive Maintenance Framework (SPMF) as a key reference. The SPMF was built on different levels, including the system’s Reliability, Availability, Maintainability and Safety (RAMS) factors, the operational environment and the available maintenance resources.

1.4.2 ANN in fault prognostics

Prediction results are a key source of data that may be incorporated into maintenance management systems. Several research works have recently investigated the most advanced and effective ML-based methods to estimate the RUL and predict the failure of a component, machine or system utilising various available datasets.

Most research works link failure prognostics, including RUL estimation and failure prediction, to PdM based on ML techniques [143], [144]. Using the error-back propagation (EBP) training algorithm along with a multilayer perceptron (MLP) architecture, Leh et al. [145] developed an approach to predict electricity transmission line breakdowns.

Einabadi et al. [84] suggested an Industry 4.0-based PdM framework for real-time RUL prediction of a machine component using ANN to assist in maintenance activities scheduling and reduce maintenance costs and the number of shutdowns in the automotive industry. Similarly, Bourezza and Mousrij [105] proposed a PdM method that included condition data acquisition, analysis, failure detection and RUL estimation. The primary goal of such a method is to assist maintenance experts and technicians in deciding how to plan, organise and conduct maintenance operations. Moreover, PdM architectures could be developed using data-driven (ML-based) models. Calabrese et al. [95] employed machine learning methods to predict the failure probability and the RUL of an industrial woodworking machine. Deep learning was used to estimate the RUL through a cycle-consistent learning scheme [146] or deep representation regularisation [147]. Li et al. [148] also implemented deep learning-based RUL estimation methods to address potential sensor failures; the results confirmed that the developed methods are suitable for real industrial applications due to the accurate RUL estimation performance.

Yan et al. [98] suggested an Industrial Big Data processing strategy in order to give new solutions to implement PdM. The method is based on organising multisource heterogeneous data, characterising it, modelling unseen elements and applying PdM using ML techniques like ANN. A real case study was presented to estimate the RUL of a vital machine tool component. Another PdM method based on RUL prediction was developed by Han et al. [149], considering the dependence of manufacturing components on product quality standards. A method for calculating maintenance costs was also developed based on the dynamic RUL prediction of the created PdM model. The proposed method confirmed the potential of the manufacturing system to carry out production duties with excellent product quality and low maintenance costs.

To improve the predictions of equipment degradation and the estimations of the RUL, Xu et al. [150] developed a “one-step” method to deal with incomplete and noisy data using ensembles of Echo State Networks, which led to producing RUL estimates of the manufacturing system components with the associated uncertainty; the validation results of this method outperformed the traditional data-driven methods.

ANN has been employed in many other applications, such as failure prediction and RUL estimation of wind turbine components [151], [152], [153], lifetime estimation of concrete bridges [154] and failure prediction of electrical motors [155],[156]. Recurrent neural network (RNN) based fault prognostics techniques for brushless DC (BLDC) motors were suggested by [157], [158], [159], including failure prediction and RUL estimation.

ANNs are likely to perform well in the RUL prediction of complex systems [160]. It is worth mentioning that various types of ANNs, such as recurrent neural networks (RNN), fuzzy neural networks (FNN) and deep convolution neural networks, were used in machinery RUL estimation and health prognostics [161], [162], [163], [164], [165], [166]. Moreover, de Pater and Mitici [167] used another type of ANN called long short-term memory (LSTM) autoencoder to develop condition indicators of an aircraft engine to use it then as input data for RUL estimation exploiting a similarity-based matching approach; this development resulted in an improved RUL estimation with more than 19% reduction in the prediction error. Likewise, Berghout et al. [168] developed an RUL estimation model for an aircraft engine based on different models, such as Denoising Online Sequential Extreme Learning Machine (DOS-ELM) with double dynamic forgetting factors (DDFF) and Updated Selection Strategy (USS) to extract more meaningful features from the available run-to-failure data. Comparison

findings confirmed the efficiency of the developed method for feature extraction and RUL estimation.

1.4.3 ANN-NBN training algorithm

The Neuron-by-Neuron (NBN) algorithm is an improved version of the Levenberg-Marquardt (LM) second-order training algorithm [169]. The LM technique is efficient and quick. However, it can only train multilayer perceptron (MLP) network architectures and solve a limited number of input patterns [170]. NBN showed improvement in computation speed and memory usage. In addition, it can handle the training with less number of neurons, it can have up to 1000 times less number of iterations compared to the EBP algorithm, it can deal with a large number of input patterns (an infinite number of patterns), and it eliminates the disability of the earlier training algorithms to deal with other types of network architectures, such as fully connected networks (FCNs) and arbitrarily connected networks (ACNs) [170], [171], [172]. Using such network architectures offers a practical way to model the complicated connections in manufacturing systems due to the massive amounts of data flowing from and between the sophisticated machinery structure of a manufacturing system. Hunter et al. [170] used several training algorithms, including the LM, EBP and NBN, to perform a comparative analysis to determine the proper network architecture and size. The study found that the NBN and LM are 100 to 1000 times quicker than the EBP algorithm.

Models may be trained using either feed-forward-backward computations or feed-forward-only calculations with NBN. When comparing the feed-forward-only process to the backpropagation in an 8x8 ASCII character identification test, the feed-forward-only process took 5.9% of the backpropagation in time. Similarly, the memory cost of the NBN method was just 4% of the LM algorithm for the so-called MNIST problem [173], [174], [175], [176].

Lastly, Hussain et al. [177] used the NBN training method in combination with an FCN architecture to develop estimators from sensor measurements of an aircraft. The developed estimator could deliver a highly accurate prediction using a small number of neurons.

1.4.4 Reliability estimation and life degradation prediction

Lu et al. [178] proposed a 3-step method to estimate the reliability and predict the RUL of bearings based on the proportional hazard model. In comparison, Chen et al. [37] used the logistic regression model to estimate the reliability of cutting tools under different failure thresholds.

Si et al. [179] used combined Bayesian and expectation maximisation (EM) algorithms to develop a degradation path-based approach to estimate the reliability and RUL. Similarly, Tang et al. [180] developed an approximate analytical RUL distribution estimation based on the maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) approach. The results showed that taking into consideration the measuring errors that exist in the degradation process can improve the real-time RUL prediction accuracy.

Different probabilistic estimation approaches were developed for the failure prediction of mechanical components. O'Dowd et al. [181] proposed a parameter estimation model based on the Bayesian approach to implementing the fully non-linear failure forecast method (FFM). Zhu et al. [182] developed a probabilistic methodology to model the damage accumulation of railway axles. Moreover, they assessed the fatigue reliability and predicted the service life of the railway based on the probabilistic distribution of fatigue over time using the same methodology. Similarly, Ma et al. [183] proposed a probabilistic prediction method for the degradation of corrosion strength for flexural beams based on Bayesian updating methods and field inspection results.

Different ML models were used to develop probabilistic estimation methods. Machine bearings degradation assessment methodology was developed by Widodo and Yang [184] utilising condition monitoring (CM) censored data. Kaplan-Meier (KM) and probability density function (PDF) estimators were used to estimate the survival probability, and relevance vector machine (RVM), which is a generalised linear model of support vector machines (SVM), was used to model the run-to-failure data and predict the survival probability of a single machine's component.

You et al. [185] used ANN to predict the probability of the daily egg production of different breeders. Mallick [39] used feed-forward ANN with backpropagation to estimate the Weibull distribution parameters for reliability analysis. Different scenarios of failure data were developed and used to train and test the developed models. Similarly, Machado-Fernández et al. [186] used ANN to estimate the Weibull distribution parameters of the sea clutters based on real-time operating conditions. In another application, Carney et al. [187] used the ensembled mixture density networks to predict the probability distribution of the surf height; the methodology is presented in a web-based application for a more user-friendly manner.

Chapter 2.

METHODS, DATA AND ANALYSIS TOOLS

2.1 Machine learning models

Machine learning (ML), or the so-called data-driven approach, is one of the most researched areas of artificial intelligence (AI) and is widely used for fault prognostics, condition monitoring and PdM, which comprises prediction and optimisation methods to discover knowledge and make smart decisions [188]. To learn models, ML or the data-driven approach [75] utilises historical data of a specific system's behaviour. When the needed historical data is available, ML techniques are employed extensively in maintenance planning and scheduling activities [75], [189], [190]. **Figure 2.1** shows the main categories of ML and example techniques for each category. According to how the learning is conducted, the most popular ML categorisation divides the techniques into three categories. In supervised learning, the software is fed with labelled training data that can be used to determine the patterns of the desired outcome. While in unsupervised learning, there is no training data used to tell what the desired result is. It is up to the programmed algorithm to find patterns in the unlabelled data. Supervised learning is mainly used for prediction based on historical data, like the stock market, whereas unsupervised learning is used mainly in clustering and dimensionality reduction [188]. Moreover, in reinforcement learning, an intelligent agent (computer programme) interacts with its surroundings and learns to respond accordingly [191].

Figure 2.1. Machine learning - main categories

2.1.1 Artificial neural networks (ANN)

One of the most popular machine learning techniques is artificial neural networks (ANN). The neural networks are designed to imitate the activities of biological brain networks. The fundamental component of neural networks is the neuron, whose size and shape can change based on what functions it performs. The ANNs consist of node layers: an input layer, an output layer, and one or multiple hidden layers, as depicted in **Figure 2.2**. The inputs, weights, summation function, and activation function can all be used to outline the overall process [169].

The nodes are connected; they all have a weight and a threshold. If the value of a node reaches the threshold, it is activated, and the data is passed through.

Figure 2.2. Sample of the basic components of an ANN

The inputs are the collected data from the main provided sources (**Figure 2.2**). The weights regulate how the inputs affect the neuron; they are continuously being changed to optimise the inputs-output relationship. The net inputs are calculated by the weighted summation function. The summation function's net input is accepted by the activation (transfer) function, which then uses it to determine the neuron's output, knowing that the activation functions are linear or non-linear algebraic equations used to make the network able to store the different relationships between the inputs and the outputs during the training process. Finally, the outputs take and accept the results provided by the activation function to be presented for further processing outside the network. The computation methods of calculating the gradient vector and the Jacobian matrix during the training process can be forward-backward or forward-only.

The selection of the suitable activation function is a challenging task, but it mainly relies on the network structure. The most used activation functions are hyperbolic tangent (tanh), softmax, identity, log sigmoid, ReLU and much more. **Table 2.1** summarises the activation functions used in this dissertation for ANN training.

Table 2.1. Summary of the used activation functions

Activation function	Graphical presentation	Mathematical description
hyperbolic tangent (tanh)		$f(x) = \frac{e^x - e^{-x}}{e^x + e^{-x}} \quad (2.1)$
Soft max (softmax)		$f(x) = \frac{\exp(x)}{\text{sum}(\exp(x))} \quad (2.2)$
Identity		$f(x) = x \quad (2.3)$
Positive linear		$f(x) = x, \text{ if } x \geq 0; \\ = 0, \text{ if } x \leq 0 \quad (2.4)$
Non-linear (positive codomain)		$f \in \mathbb{R}^+ \quad (2.5)$
Quadratic function		$f(x) = x^2 \quad (2.6)$

2.1.2 Artificial neural network training algorithms and network architectures

Training the neural networks is a complicated process. Selecting the proper architecture and training algorithm can determine the success of an application. Different training algorithms are used to train the developed neural networks. The most popular one is the error-back propagation algorithm (EBP) which is an inefficient algorithm [170]. Among the usually used algorithms, EBP works with many errors; it is slower and inefficient compared to the other newly developed second-order training algorithms, such as Levenberg–Marquardt (LM) and the Neuron-by-Neuron (NBN) algorithms [169].

Multi-layer perceptron (MLP) is the most popular neural network architecture. However, MLP is inefficient and not powerful due to the high number of the required neurons to solve problems with a limited number of patterns [170], [171], [173], [192]. Thus, ACN and FCN are better and more efficient compared to the MLP [171], [173], [177]. **Figure 2.3** shows examples of MLP, ACN and FCN network architectures.

Figure 2.3. Different artificial neural network architectures
 A: FCN / 2 inputs, 1 output; B: ACN / 2 inputs, 2 outputs; C: MLP 2-3-1

2.1.3 Performance metrics

The developed models were evaluated in terms of their prediction accuracy using different performance metrics as below.

- 1- The sum squared error (SSE) is the main statistical performance index that was used to evaluate the trained models. For all patterns and outputs, SSE is calculated as follows:

$$SSE = \sum_{i=1}^{np} (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2 \tag{2.7}$$

Where np is the number of patterns, \hat{y}_i is the predicted value, and y_i is the target (measured) value.

- 2- The prediction error in terms of the estimated RUL is calculated using Eq. (2.8).

$$\text{Prediction error} = |RUL_e - RUL_{ANN}| \quad (2.8)$$

Where RUL_{ANN} is the predicted RUL by the developed ANN model and RUL_e is the expected RUL based on the expected degradation path of the testing dataset.

- 3- The absolute and relative errors were calculated according to Eq. (2.9) and Eq. (2.10).

$$\text{Absolute error} = |ft_{ANN} - ft_e| \quad (2.9)$$

$$\text{Relative error} = \frac{|ft_{ANN} - ft_e|}{ft_e} \quad (2.10)$$

Where, ft_e is the expected failure time, and ft_{ANN} is the predicted failure time.

- 4- The root-mean-square error (RMSE) is a statistical performance measure and is calculated using Eq. (2.11).

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^{np} (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2}{np}} \quad (2.11)$$

Where np is the number of patterns, \hat{y}_i is the predicted value, and y_i is the target (measured) value.

There is no standard threshold for the accepted SSE or RMSE [193], but we can use them for comparisons, the low RMSE value indicates that the actual and predicted data are close to each other, showing a better accuracy. Thus, the lower RMSE indicates the better model performance.

Coefficient of determination (R^2) represents the variance proportion in the dependent variables that can be explained by the developed model. The closer its value to 1, the better the developed model in predicting the dependent variables. R^2 can be calculated as Eq. (2.12).

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{np} (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^{no} (y_i - \bar{y})^2} \quad (2.12)$$

Where np is the number of patterns, \hat{y}_i is the predicted value, y_i is the target (measured) value, and \bar{y} is the mean value of the target (measured) values.

The good values of $R^2 > 85\%$ (the closer to 1 is the better) indicate that the developed models have a good and acceptable prediction ability.

2.1.4 ANN Basic mathematical formulations

Assume that we have neuron j with ni inputs, as shown in **Figure 2.4**.

Figure 2.4. Neuron j connection with the rest of the network

The output node of a neuron j is calculated by

$$y_j = f_j(net_j) \quad (2.13)$$

where net_j is the sum of the weighted input nodes of the j^{th} neuron as follows

$$net_j = \sum_{i=1}^{ni} y_{j,i} w_{j,i} + w_{j,0} \quad (2.14)$$

In this equation $y_{j,i}$ is the i^{th} input node of the j^{th} neuron weighted by $w_{j,i}$, and $w_{j,0}$ is the bias weight of neuron j . $f_j(\cdot)$ is the activation function for the j^{th} neuron. Derivation of Eq. (2.14) is

$$\frac{\partial net_j}{\partial w_{j,i}} = y_{j,i} \quad (2.15)$$

And the slope s_j of the activation function $f_j(\cdot)$ is

$$s_j = \frac{\partial y_j}{\partial net_j} = \frac{\partial f_j(net_j)}{\partial net_j} \quad (2.16)$$

There is a complex non-linear relationship between the network output o_m and the output node y_j of the neuron j :

$$o_m = F_{m,j}(y_j) \quad (2.17)$$

where o_m is the m^{th} network output.

The updated rule of the EBP algorithm is

$$\mathbf{w}_{n+1} = \mathbf{w}_n - \varphi \mathbf{g}_n \quad (2.18)$$

Where n is the iteration index, \mathbf{w} is the vector of weights, φ is the learning constant, and \mathbf{g} is the gradient vector.

2.2 Simulation of degradation data of mechanical components

Highly reliable failure datasets are rare. According to [194], failure data can be classified into three main types:

1. Lifetime data from comparable devices over time, demonstrating how long it took them to fail.
2. A predefined condition indicator threshold value that identifies the failure once it is reached.
3. Historical run-to-failure data of machines showing similar behaviour to the one we need to diagnose.

The main burden of our research is the lack of available data. Therefore, simulated degradation data with a predefined failure threshold was used to conduct this study.

There are two methods to get such reliability information. The first one is to measure some of the parameters that characterise the degradation (ageing over time) of the unit (component), while the other one is to manipulate the covariates (e.g., temperature, pressure or speed) to accelerate the degradation process during the experimentations and get the required reliability information faster. These methods can also be combined [195].

The degradation data are considered as Health / Condition Indicators (HI / CI) of the analysed system. It is expected that the HI parameters have monotonic values [196], which means that the HI parameters have increasing or decreasing trends with increasing degradation [197].

In many situations, run-to-failure (lifespan) data is not captured, but the required failure threshold values can be identified from the available information with a predefined threshold by the manufacturer. For instance, the temperature of the liquid in a pump should not exceed 80 °C. Thus, such data can be used to set a HI model based on the recorded data from the sensory system, e.g., temperature, voltage or pressure, which fluctuates over time. These degradation models can be used to estimate the RUL once the condition indicator crosses the predefined threshold.

Data simulation assumptions are based on the methodology of Bagdonavičius and Nikulin [195] to simulate (lifetime data) degradation models from data with covariates.

Assume that the efficiency level of a mechanical component is described by an increasing stochastic function $Z(t)$.

The functional form of the mean degradation $m(t) = \mathbf{E}(Z(t))$ is known in most cases.

As an example, if the mean degradation of a component $m(t)$ gradually decreases in time and becomes constant after a short period of time at a value γ_0 , then the mean degradation can be modelled as follows:

$$m(t) = \gamma_0 t + \frac{\gamma_1}{\gamma_2} (1 - e^{-\gamma_2 t}), \quad \text{where } \gamma_i > 0 \quad (2.19)$$

If the relative mean of the degradation is a non-linear function, then

$$d(t) = (1 + \gamma_0 t^{\gamma_1})^{-1} \quad (2.20)$$

And the mean degradation can be calculated as

$$m(t) = \gamma_0 t^{\gamma_1} \quad (2.21)$$

Here, $m(0) = 0$ and the mean degradation is increasing. There exists a one-to-one correspondence between the values of $m(t)$ and $d(t)$.

Assume that the distribution of $Z(t)$ and $\Delta Z(t) = Z(t + \Delta t) - Z(t)$ are from the same family, and the gamma-process with right-continuous trajectories is the independent increments of $Z(t)$, so.

$$Z(t) = \sigma^2 \gamma(t) \quad (2.22)$$

Where σ is the variance and $\gamma(t)$ is a process with independent increments:

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma(t) &\sim G\left(1, v(t)\right) = G\left(1, \frac{m(t)}{\sigma^2}\right), \quad \Delta \gamma(t) = \gamma(t + \Delta t) - \gamma(t) \\ &\sim G\left(1, \frac{\Delta m(t)}{\sigma^2}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (2.23)$$

Where $v(t)$ is the shape parameter of the gamma-process.

If $\gamma(t)$ has a gamma distribution with scale parameter 1 and shape parameter $v(t) = m(t)/\sigma^2$, then the mean is $\mathbf{E}(Z(t)) = m(t)$ and the variance is $\mathbf{Var}(Z(t)) = \sigma^2 m(t)$. When $Z(t)$ reaches the value z_0 , a failure takes place due to the degradation.

The moment of failure is defined as follows:

$$t_f = \sup\{t: Z(t) < z_0\} = \inf\{t: Z(t) \geq z_0\}$$

For simulation purposes, we have the following assumption:

T (time horizon of the simulation) = 4, n (number of points) = 1000, $\sigma = 0.2$ and $\Delta t = T/n = 0.004$.

From Eq. (2.22), assume that the expected value of the degradation path at time t : $m(t) = (0.3 \tanh [t - 2]) - (0.3 \tanh [-2])$

Then, substituting it into Eq. (2.23) we can simulate the degradation process.

Figure 2.5 shows the initial results of the simulation.

Figure 2.5. Initialisation of the simulated degradation dataset

Now, suppose that the failure threshold is $z_0 = 0.3$, and the degradation level is $\text{Var}(Z(t)) = \sigma^2 m(t)$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Var}(Z(t)) &= \sigma^2 m(t), & z_0 < 0.3 \\ \text{Var}(Z(t)) &= 0, & z_0 \geq 0.3 \end{aligned} \tag{2.24}$$

Substituting into Eq. (2.24), the resulted degradation path is shown in Figure 2.6.

Figure 2.6. Sample of simulated degradation training dataset along with predefined failure threshold

The system fails when the degradation measure surpasses the predefined threshold of 0.3. The component is replaced with a new one (perfect maintenance), and the degradation process is reinitialised to zero.

For data pre-processing, the dataset is prepared for the training phase. Input datasets are pre-processed by removing outliers and missing values in the first step. Then, as a general step in the case of having a multi-input system (multi-features), a feature selection method is implemented to include the most influential ones in the modelling process (in our case study, we have only one input feature which is the degradation time step in which the replacement occurs). Finally, the training and testing datasets are ready for the modelling process. Moreover, the failure threshold of the degradation data is defined, and the dataset variables are normalised if necessary.

The normalisation of inputs is essential since it speeds up the learning process and leads to a quicker convergence [97]. The min-max normalisation method is presented in Eq. (2.25)

$$x' = \frac{x - \min(x)}{\max(x) - \min(x)} \quad 2.25$$

Where x' is the normalised value, and x is the value to be normalised; $\min(x)$ and $\max(x)$ are the minimum and maximum values of the range from which x' has been normalised.

Table 2.2 summarises the main properties of the simulated degradation dataset.

Table 2.2. Summary of the main properties of the training dataset

Total count	Mean	Standard deviation	Failure threshold (h)
6323	0.09445	0.09967	0.3

Figure 2.7-A shows the overall simulated failure prediction dataset, and **Figure 2.7-B** shows the magnification of the dataset by which the prediction is tested.

Figure 2.7. A: The full simulated failure prediction dataset with its predefined failure threshold

B: Magnification of the testing dataset (failure prediction area)

2.3 Simulation of decreased gearbox efficiency data of wind turbine

CMSs include sensors, data acquisition, data processing, cabling, and other installations that provide continuous and real-time information on the monitored component condition [28], [29]. Statistical algorithms are one of the most exploited analysis methods in CM of WTs [135], side by side with different types of machine learning (ML) techniques, such as Artificial Neural Network (ANN), Standard Classification and Regression Tree (CART), Boosting Tree Algorithm (BTA), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest (RF), Decision Tree (DT) and much more [198], [126], [127], [138], [199], [200], [201], [202], [203], [204], [205].

The supervisory control and data acquisition (SCADA) system is a crucial component of wind turbine process performance and condition monitoring systems and is not easy to obtain. SCADA systems can provide a wide range of measurements, including temperature, wind speed, wind direction, rotor speed,

pitch angle and output power. These characteristics are frequently used to check on the health of wind farm operations. Due to its high availability, SCADA data has been used in numerous studies to estimate wind speed and power [201]. In addition to CMS sensors, the SCADA system also uses many sensors to collect data. The SCADA system monitors signals and alarms at typically ten-minute intervals [198], [128].

The used wind turbine dataset to verify and test the developed performance monitoring method in **Chapter 6** is a simulated (artificial) SCADA data using the FAST-NREL (USA Government based, National Renewable Energy Laboratory) simulating software as described in detail in [206]. Three different gearbox efficiency levels of the WT “DeWindD6 – 1250 kW” are considered, knowing that the gearbox efficiency can be degraded because of the lack of lubricant, high temperature and mechanical losses (torque losses) due to the friction between the gears of the high-speed shaft (HSS) and the low-speed shaft (LSS). Each level consisted of different percentages of gearbox efficiency. Moreover, the torques of the HSS and LSS (**Figure 2.8**) are computed during the simulation based on Eq. (2.26) and Eq. (2.27), taking into consideration the gearbox efficiency.

$$\text{HSS torque} = \text{LSS torque} \times \text{gearbox ratio} \times \text{efficiency} \quad (2.26)$$

$$\text{LSS torque} = \frac{\text{HSS torque}}{\text{gearbox ratio} \times \text{efficiency}} \quad (2.27)$$

Figure 2.8. Main components of the WT

Figure 2.9 depicts the main causes of the potential gearbox efficiency decreasing, resulting in degraded generated power.

Figure 2.9. Simplified cause-and-effect diagram of the main problem considered in the study.

In this study, three data features are considered: average wind speed, gearbox efficiency and generated active power (Table 2.3). The gearbox degradation of each efficiency level of the WT is indicated by the decreased gearbox efficiency.

Table 2.3. Selected input features of SCADA data

No.	Input Feature
1	Average wind speed
2	Gearbox Efficiency %
3	Generated active power

Each efficiency level includes one thousand measurements of ten minutes of average wind speed per simulation, its associated generated active power and one efficiency percentage (i.e., 100%, 97% or 90%). Figure 2.10 depicts the simulated ten-minute average wind speed of 1000 observations (measurements); a single data point represents the average wind speed from 3-18 m/s of ten minutes duration.

Figure 2.10. Ten minutes average sample simulated wind speed 3-18 m/s

During the data pre-processing, transient time data, outliers, missing values, and measurements below the cut-in (wind speed in which power generation starts)

and above the cut-off wind speed (wind speed in which power generation stops) of each feature measurement were neglected (focusing on power production areas only).

Figure 2.11 depicts three efficiency levels which have different decreasing gearbox efficiencies due to the gearbox degradation, in addition to the box plot of the simulated power for each level.

Figure 2.11. Box plot of the simulated generated power and gearbox decreasing efficiencies of the different efficiency levels

The so-called power curve, defined as mean wind speed and its corresponding active power, is frequently used to show the power generated by the WT. A sample scatter plot of the power curve for two different efficiency levels (97% and 90% gearbox efficiencies, respectively) is shown in **Figure 2.12**.

Figure 2.12. Power curve profiles of a generated measurements sample

Table 2.4 summarises the main parameters and the ideal operating conditions of DeWindD6 WT used in the simulation process of the different efficiency levels. The simulation tools, simulation of meteorological conditions, wind speed averaging method, and simulation control characteristics of the developed efficiency levels are available in detail in [206]. Complete technical characteristics of the DeWindD6 WT are available in [207].

Table 2.4. The operating parameters used in the simulation process

Cut-in speed (m/s)	Cut-out speed (m/s)	Rated speed (m/s)	Rated power (kW)	Total run time per measurement (minutes)	Air density (kg/m ³)	Turbulence intensity (%)	Mean wind speed of the reference height (m/s)	Hub Height (m)	Gearbox efficiency (%)
2.8	23	12.5	1250	12	1.225	0-20	3-18	84.672	90-100

The power curve of any wind turbine in real applications is dynamic because of the constantly changing working conditions, such as the weather, temperature, wind speed, air density, system controls and humidity. As a result, the variation in wind speed affects different parameters, such as rotor speed, pitch angle, and the generated power [208]. The wind speed and the desired rotor speed of the WT based on its power curve determine the best pitch angle of the blades; the optimum wind direction gives the maximum generated power when it is perpendicular to the blades. Overall, wind speed variations lead to a change in the generated power.

2.4 Software and data analysis tools

All models in this dissertation were developed and analysed using a laptop with the following specifications.

Processor: Intel (R) Core (TM) i7-8750H CPU @ 2.20GHz (12 CPUs), 2.2 GHz

Memory: 12288 MB RAM

Different software packages and statistical analysis tools were used for data pre-processing, results visualisation, model development and data analysis as they are shown below.

- 1- **Microsoft excel**
- 2- **IBM SPSS statistics 26**
- 3- **Minitab 16**
- 4- **Wolfram Mathematica 12**
- 5- **Matlab R2021b**
- 6- **Stat soft -STATISTICA**
- 7- **NBN trainer 2.0**
- 8- **OriginPro 2021**
- 9- **Draw.io**

Chapter 3.

FAULT PROGNOSTICS OF MECHANICAL COMPONENTS USING ANN

3.1 Introduction

Fault prognostics aims at predicting potential failures and estimating the RUL of the different components of manufacturing systems; it can be considered the main activity of intelligent maintenance, complying with the emerged requirements of Industry 4.0 integration.

The developed fault prognostic method based on the novel data-driven approach in this research is verified and analysed using a simulated degradation dataset with a predefined failure threshold of a single mechanical component discussed in **section 2.2**.

The RUL may also be used as an important risk indicator, indicating how long a machine can generally run before breaking down [209], [210]. The inputs to the RUL estimation model are usually considered condition indicators or features taken from the sensory system or recorded by the machine operators or maintenance personnel. Thus, estimating the RUL in PdM plans is highly prioritised [194]. In this chapter, a novel data-driven prognostic analysis approach for predicting the failure of a mechanical component based on its degradation path and estimating the RUL is proposed.

3.2 Methodology

The proposed methodology for fault prognostics of mechanical components consists of five phases as the following:

1. Degradation data simulation: Where the needed input degradation measurements are acquired from real or experimental sources. For model verification purposes, the required degradation data is simulated based on a well-known degradation law to be used for training and testing the proposed model, as discussed in **section 2.2**.
2. Data pre-processing: The mechanical component's degradation dataset is prepared for the training phase, as discussed in **section 2.2**.
3. Model construction: The required network design, activation functions, training algorithm and related parameters are selected.

4. Training phase: The constructed model is trained with the pre-processed degradation data.
5. Prediction phase: The trained model gives predictions for the degradation path and the extrapolated expected degradation path, which leads to predicting the potential failure point and then estimating the RUL of the component.
6. Further processing: This phase involves visualising the prediction results for further processing, such as decision-making or maintenance planning.

These phases are discussed thoroughly in this chapter.

Figure 3.1 shows the flowchart of the proposed methodology.

Figure 3.1. Fault prognostics methodology flowchart

Regarding the accepted training error, different runs of the initial version of the developed model were performed with different values of the main parameters such as the number of neurons, number of hidden layers, learning rate and number of iterations. The initial values of the parameters were set based on the gained experience of the used network architectures and training algorithms in similar studies [145], [147], [148].

The error (i.e., RMSE) is calculated for each run and the least error is accepted.

The error of such applications should not exceed a specific limit such as 0.025 RMSE [211], [143], [144].

For other ML models developed using software packages such as SPSS, the model parameters were tuned automatically by the software based on the input data, this was applied using an optimization function called “expert modeller” which will produce the least error as much as possible, then if the error is greater than 0.025, the method should be changed.

3.3 Improvement of the NBN training algorithm

3.3.1 NBN training algorithm

The NBN training algorithm has various benefits over the other training algorithms, including the capability to handle neural networks with arbitrary connections and feed forward-only computation, in addition to the direct computation of quasi-Hessian matrices without the need to compute and store the Jacobian matrix. These computations are discussed below.

The NBN training algorithm is an improved form of the second-order LM algorithm [169]. The updated rule of the LM algorithm, according to [169], [171], [212] was derived from the Newton algorithm and the steepest descent method as the following.

$$\mathbf{w}_{n+1} = \mathbf{w}_n - (J_n^T J_n + \eta I)^{-1} J_n \mathbf{e}_n \quad (3.1)$$

Where n is the iteration index, J is the Jacobian matrix, I is the identity matrix, η is the combination coefficient, and \mathbf{e} is the error vector. The construction of the Jacobian matrix is shown by Eq. (3.2), where p is the training pattern, j is the neuron index, and $w_{j,x}$ is the x^{th} connection weight to neuron j . In the Jacobian matrix, there are no rows for every training pattern p , where no is the number of outputs of the network. The number of columns of J is equal to the number of weights in the network, and the number of rows is $np \times no$ [174], [169].

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \text{neuron 1} \quad \dots \quad \text{neuron } j \quad \dots \\
 \left[\begin{array}{cccc}
 \frac{\partial e_{1,1}}{\partial w_{1,1}} & \frac{\partial e_{1,1}}{\partial w_{1,2}} & \dots & \frac{\partial e_{1,1}}{\partial w_{j,1}} & \frac{\partial e_{1,1}}{\partial w_{j,2}} & \dots \\
 \frac{\partial e_{1,2}}{\partial w_{1,1}} & \frac{\partial e_{1,2}}{\partial w_{1,2}} & \dots & \frac{\partial e_{1,2}}{\partial w_{j,1}} & \frac{\partial e_{1,2}}{\partial w_{j,2}} & \dots \\
 \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\
 \frac{\partial e_{1,no}}{\partial w_{1,1}} & \frac{\partial e_{1,no}}{\partial w_{1,2}} & \dots & \frac{\partial e_{1,no}}{\partial w_{j,1}} & \frac{\partial e_{1,no}}{\partial w_{j,2}} & \dots \\
 \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\
 \frac{\partial e_{p,1}}{\partial w_{1,1}} & \frac{\partial e_{p,1}}{\partial w_{1,2}} & \dots & \frac{\partial e_{p,1}}{\partial w_{j,1}} & \frac{\partial e_{p,1}}{\partial w_{j,2}} & \dots \\
 \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\
 \frac{\partial e_{p,m}}{\partial w_{1,1}} & \frac{\partial e_{p,m}}{\partial w_{1,2}} & \dots & \frac{\partial e_{p,m}}{\partial w_{j,1}} & \frac{\partial e_{p,m}}{\partial w_{j,2}} & \dots \\
 \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\
 \frac{\partial e_{np,1}}{\partial w_{1,1}} & \frac{\partial e_{np,1}}{\partial w_{1,2}} & \dots & \frac{\partial e_{np,1}}{\partial w_{j,1}} & \frac{\partial e_{np,1}}{\partial w_{j,2}} & \dots \\
 \frac{\partial e_{np,2}}{\partial w_{1,1}} & \frac{\partial e_{np,2}}{\partial w_{1,2}} & \dots & \frac{\partial e_{np,2}}{\partial w_{j,1}} & \frac{\partial e_{np,2}}{\partial w_{j,2}} & \dots \\
 \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\
 \frac{\partial e_{np,no}}{\partial w_{1,1}} & \frac{\partial e_{np,no}}{\partial w_{1,2}} & \dots & \frac{\partial e_{np,no}}{\partial w_{j,1}} & \frac{\partial e_{np,no}}{\partial w_{j,2}} & \dots
 \end{array} \right]
 \end{array}
 \begin{array}{l}
 \left. \begin{array}{l} m = 1 \\ m = 2 \\ \dots \\ m = no \end{array} \right\} p = 1 \\
 \dots \\
 \left. \begin{array}{l} m = 1 \\ \dots \\ m = m \end{array} \right\} p = p \\
 \dots \\
 \left. \begin{array}{l} m = 1 \\ m = 2 \\ \dots \\ m = no \end{array} \right\} p = np
 \end{array}
 \quad (3.2)$$

The Jacobian matrix elements can be calculated using

$$\frac{\partial e_m}{\partial w_{j,i}} = \frac{\partial e_m}{\partial y_j} \frac{\partial y_j}{\partial net_j} \frac{\partial net_j}{\partial w_{j,i}} \quad (3.3)$$

By combining (2.15), (2.16) and (2.17), Eq. (3.3) can be written as

$$\frac{\partial e_m}{\partial w_{j,i}} = y_{j,i} s_j F'_{m,j} \quad (3.4)$$

Parameter δ is used to measure the EBP process in second-order algorithms as

$$\delta_{m,j} = s_j F'_{m,j} \quad (3.5)$$

Combining Eq. (3.4) and (2.13), the Jacobian matrix element can be calculated using

$$\frac{\partial e_m}{\partial w_{i,i}} = y_{j,i} \delta_{m,j} \quad (3.6)$$

In the backpropagation process, the error is replaced by 1.

In most cases, the Jacobian matrix is generated and stored to update the weights using Eq. (3.1). This is useful in cases that require a few training patterns. Due to the massive size of the Jacobian matrix [174], memory restriction may become a

key challenge to be addressed for larger numbers of training patterns. The weights in the NBN algorithm are adjusted using the following update rule:

$$\mathbf{w}_{n+1} = \mathbf{w}_n - (Q + \eta I)^{-1} \mathbf{g} \quad (3.7)$$

Where Q is the quasi-Hessian matrix and \mathbf{g} is the gradient vector. This is an updated form of the LM rule [169].

Where

$$Q = J^T J \quad (3.8)$$

$$\mathbf{g} = J^T \mathbf{e} \quad (3.9)$$

However, in the NBN algorithm, the matrix Q is calculated by summing the quasi-Hessian sub-matrix $\theta_{p,m}$ for pattern p and network output neuron m :

$$Q = \sum_{p=1}^{np} \sum_{m=1}^{no} \theta_{p,m} \quad (3.10)$$

The gradient vector \mathbf{g} is calculated by summing the gradient sub-vector $\boldsymbol{\eta}_{p,m}$ for pattern p and network output neuron m :

$$\mathbf{g} = \sum_{p=1}^{np} \sum_{m=1}^{no} \boldsymbol{\eta}_{p,m} \quad (3.11)$$

The size of the matrix Q is $n \times n$ and is independent of the number of patterns and outputs.

The NBN algorithm, unlike the LM algorithm, immediately calculates the matrix Q and vector \mathbf{g} when the patterns are applied. As a result, the Jacobian matrix (J) does not need to be computed or stored [169]. The vector $\mathbf{j}_{p,m}$ is calculated as the patterns are applied to achieve this. The Jacobian row for pattern p and network output neuron m is represented by this vector $\mathbf{j}_{p,m}$. The matrix Q and vector \mathbf{g} can be updated using this vector as each pattern is applied using the following equations:

$$\theta_{p,m} = \mathbf{j}_{p,m}^T \mathbf{j}_{p,m} \quad (3.12)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\eta}_{p,m} = \mathbf{j}_{p,m} e_{p,m} \quad (3.13)$$

Forward-only computation is an improved form of NBN computations used to improve the efficiency of the Jacobian matrix computations by eliminating the backpropagation process to avoid repeating the backpropagation process for each output in case of having a network with multiple outputs [169], [175].

From Eq. (3.5), $\delta_{m,j}$ is considered as a signal gain between the network output m and the net input of neuron j . If we extend this concept between all neurons, as depicted in **Figure 3.2** and **Figure 3.3**, $\delta_{k,j}$ becomes the extension of Eq. (3.5) as the signal gain between neurons j and k .

$$\delta_{k,j} = \frac{\partial F_{k,j}(y_j)}{\partial net_j} = \frac{\partial F_{k,j}(y_j)}{\partial y_j} \frac{\partial y_j}{\partial net_j} = F'_{k,j} s_j \tag{3.14}$$

Where, k and j are neuron indices, $F_{k,j}(y_j)$ is the non-linear relationship between the output node of neuron j and the output node of neuron k . Gain parameters are not calculated using input or bias weights [175].

Figure 3.2. $\delta_{k,j}$ is interpreted as a signal gain, wherein a feed-forward network, neuron j must be positioned before neuron k [175]

Figure 3.3. $\delta_{k,j}$ parameters (A) of the four neurons in FCN (B).

In the feed-forward principle, the FCN must have a cascade architecture, as seen in **Figure 3.3-B**. Slopes of the activation function of the neurons s_j can be written in the form of the parameter δ as $\delta_{j,j} = s_j$ (see **Figure 3.3-A**).

In **Figure 3.3-A**, the first neuron has only one δ parameter, which can be written as

$$\delta_{1,1} = s_1 \tag{3.15}$$

While for the second neuron, there are two δ parameters written as

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_{2,2} &= s_2 \\ \delta_{2,1} &= s_2 w_{1,2} s_1 \end{aligned} \tag{3.16}$$

And so on for the rest of the neurons.

$$\delta_{k,j} = \delta_{k,k} \sum_{i=j}^{k-1} w_{i,k} \delta_{i,j} \tag{3.17}$$

Where neuron j must be located before neuron k in feed-forward computations; thus, $k \geq j$.

While $\delta_{k,k} = s_k$ is the activation function slope of neuron k , $w_{j,k}$ is the weight between neuron j and neuron k , $\delta_{k,j}$ is the signal gain through the weight $w_{j,k}$ and through other network parts connected to $w_{j,k}$.

For calculating the signal gains between neurons, an $nn \times nn$ computation table is depicted in **Figure 3.4**, where nn is the number of neurons. Here the connections between neurons are taken into consideration. However, the network input weights and all neuron biasing weights are used only at the end of the process.

Neuron index	1	2	...	j	...	k	...	nn
1	$\delta_{1,1}$	$w_{1,2}$...	$w_{1,j}$...	$w_{1,k}$...	$w_{1,nn}$
2	$\delta_{2,1}$	$\delta_{2,2}$...	$w_{2,j}$...	$w_{2,k}$...	$w_{2,nn}$
...
j	$\delta_{j,1}$	$\delta_{j,2}$...	$\delta_{j,j}$...	$w_{j,k}$...	$w_{j,nn}$
...
k	$\delta_{k,1}$	$\delta_{k,2}$...	$\delta_{k,j}$...	$\delta_{k,k}$...	$w_{k,nn}$
...
nn	$\delta_{nn,1}$	$\delta_{nn,2}$...	$\delta_{nn,j}$...	$\delta_{nn,k}$...	$\delta_{nn,nn}$

Figure 3.4. $nn \times nn$ computation table sample

In feed-forward networks, $k \geq j$, and three matrix areas can be identified, as depicted in **Figure 3.4**. The upper blue triangle includes the weights between the neurons, the light orange main diagonal is the slopes vector of the activation functions (see Eq. (3.15)), and the lower triangle is the signal gain matrix δ .

For ACN, we have the same computations, but some elements of the computation table are zeros, as shown in **Figure 3.5**. Forward-only computation is adopted to reduce the storage requirements and the computation time, where zero values weights are not stored, and computation operations are not executed with zero elements.

Neuron index	1	2	3	4	5	6
1	s_1	$w_{1,2}$	$w_{1,3}$	$w_{1,4}$	$w_{1,5}$	$w_{1,6}$
2	$\delta_{2,1}$	s_2	$w_{2,3}$	$w_{2,4}$	$w_{2,5}$	$w_{2,6}$
3	$\delta_{3,1}$	$\delta_{3,2}$	s_3	$w_{3,4}$	$w_{3,5}$	$w_{3,6}$
4	$\delta_{4,1}$	$\delta_{4,2}$	$\delta_{4,3}$	s_4	$w_{4,5}$	$w_{4,6}$
5	$\delta_{5,1}$	$\delta_{5,2}$	$\delta_{5,3}$	$\delta_{5,4}$	s_5	$w_{5,6}$
6	$\delta_{6,1}$	$\delta_{6,2}$	$\delta_{6,3}$	$\delta_{6,4}$	$\delta_{6,5}$	s_6

A

Neuron index	1	2	3	4	5	6
1	s_1	0	$w_{1,3}$	0	0	$w_{1,6}$
2	0	s_2	0	$w_{2,4}$	$w_{2,5}$	0
3	$\delta_{3,1}$	0	s_3	0	$w_{3,5}$	$w_{3,6}$
4	0	$\delta_{4,2}$	0	s_4	$w_{4,5}$	0
5	0	$\delta_{5,2}$	$\delta_{5,3}$	$\delta_{5,4}$	s_5	0
6	$\delta_{6,1}$	0	$\delta_{6,3}$	0	0	s_6

B

Figure 3.5. Six neurons in FCN (A) and ACN (B) structure

Eq. (3.17) can be completed in two steps in order to simplify further the computation process.

$$x_{k,j} = \sum_{i=j}^{k-1} w_{i,k} \delta_{i,j} \tag{3.18}$$

and

$$\delta_{k,j} = \delta_{k,k} x_{k,j} = s_k x_{k,j} \tag{3.19}$$

Figure 3.6 presents the pseudo-code of the forward-only computation of the second-order NBN algorithm.

```

for all patterns ( $p$ )
  for all neurons ( $nn$ )
    for all weights of the neurons ( $nx$ )
      calculate net; % Eq. (2.14)
    end;
    calculate neuron output; % Eq. (2.13)
    calculate neuron slope; % Eq. (2.16)
    set current slope as delta;
    for weights connected to previous neurons ( $ny$ )
      for previous neurons ( $nz$ )
        multiply delta through weights then sum; % Eq. (3.18)
      end;
      multiply the sum by the slope; % Eq. (3.19)
    end;
    related Jacobian element computation; % Eq. (3.6)
  end;
  for all outputs ( $no$ )
    calculate error; % Eq. (2.7)
  end;
end;

```

Figure 3.6. Pseudo-code of the NBN-forward-only computation [169]

3.3.1.1 Improved NBN with accumulative network design

To increase the efficiency of the trained model using the NBN training algorithm, in the first place, the neural network was extended with an accumulative step. Meanwhile, a filtering method to select a specific number of training points in each degradation cycle is included in the developed algorithm, where the “filter size” variable means how many points are neglected during the training; this step helps get rid of the high number of successive constant values which can be considered as useless for the training process. The “filter size” is calculated from the end of each degradation cycle to prevent deleting the highest point. (e.g., if the original points are {0,1,1,3,3,3,4,4,4,5} and the filter size is 3, the filtered data are the following: {0,1,1,3,3,3,4,4,4,5} and so on. **Figure 3.7** shows the filtered degradation points for training.

Figure 3.7. The filtered training points

The design of the intended network, as seen in **Figure 3.8** is based on accumulated FCN, but it can also be based on accumulated ACN; it consists of three main layers; the input layer, the processing or hidden layer and the output layer. $X_1(p)$, is the time starting when the component is replaced; “p” denotes the actual time step. The output of the network $Y_1(p)$ is predicted point of degradation. $N1 \dots N4$ are the neurons.

Figure 3.8. The network design of the improved ANN-NBN with accumulative FCN architecture

Whereas the component's degradation increases over time, the model considers that, and the network is extended with an accumulation step, resulting in a system output that is monotonously increasing.

To confirm, the NBN algorithm has various benefits over the other training algorithms, including the capability to handle neural networks with arbitrary connections and feed forward-only computation and the direct computation of quasi-Hessian matrices without the need to compute and store the Jacobian matrix. Forward-only is an improved form of NBN computations used to improve the efficiency of the Jacobian matrix computations by eliminating the backpropagation process to avoid repeating the backpropagation process for each output in case of having a network with multiple outputs [51], [55].

The improved NBN-forward-only computation algorithm with the accumulative network design is discussed in this section. In this arrangement, The actual output of the neurons in the last layer is added to their previous output. This structure and the application of such activation functions in the last layer that has a positive codomain allows us to force the output of the network to be monotone increasing, which matches the nature of the degradation processes.

In the accumulative network illustrated in **Figure 3.8**, the output of each neuron (y_j) can be calculated using the activation function $f_j(\cdot)$ and the weighted input net_i of the j^{th} neuron as in Eq. (2.13).

In the model, we use the following expression for the weighted input of the j^{th} neuron in the case of learning point p :

$$net_j = \sum_{i=1}^{\overline{IY(j)}} w_{Yp(j,i)} y_{IY(j,i)} + \sum_{i=1}^{\overline{IX(j)}} W_{Xp(j,i)} \begin{cases} d_{p-\Delta(i),IX(j,i)} & \text{if } i \leq no \\ x_{p-\Delta(i),IX(j,i)} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} + w_{Bp(j)} \quad (3.20)$$

where $w_{Yp(j,i)}$ is the weight of the j^{th} neuron for the i^{th} internal (from a previous neuron) input, $y_{IY(j,i)}$ is the i^{th} internal input of the j^{th} neuron, $\overline{IY(j)}$ is the number of internal inputs of the j^{th} neuron, $\overline{IX(j)}$ is the number of external inputs of the j^{th} neuron, $Yp(j, i)$ is the position of weight of the i^{th} internal input of the j^{th} neuron, $Xp(j, i)$ is the position of weight of the i^{th} external input of the j^{th} neuron, $Bp(j)$ is the position of the bias weight of the j^{th} neuron. The m^{th} output of the system of learning point p is denoted by

$$Y_{p,m} = y_{p,m} \quad m \in o \quad (3.21)$$

where o is the set of indices of the output neurons, and the cardinality of o is no . In the learning process, we minimise the sum squared error (SSE), where $\varepsilon_{p,m}$ is the difference of the m^{th} outputs of the system and its desired value while evaluating the p^{th} learning point:

$$\varepsilon_{p,m} = \sum_{k=1}^p Y_{k,m} - \sum_{k=1}^p d_{k,m} = \sum_{k=1}^p (Y_{k,m} - d_{k,m}) \quad (3.22)$$

The Levenberg-Marquardt weight update rule is the following:

$$\mathbf{w}^* = \mathbf{w} - (J^T J + \eta I)^{-1} \mathbf{g} \quad (3.23)$$

Where \mathbf{w}^* is the new weight vector, \mathbf{w} is the previous weight vector, J is the Jacobian matrix of the error function, η is the combination coefficient, \mathbf{g} is the gradient vector of the error function. The gradient vector can be calculated by:

$$\mathbf{g} = J \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \quad (3.24)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ is the error vector.

The Jacobian matrix is defined by the following formula:

$$J_{p,m} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \varepsilon_{p,m}}{\partial w_1} & \frac{\partial \varepsilon_{p,m}}{\partial w_2} & \dots & \frac{\partial \varepsilon_{p,m}}{\partial w_{nw}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.25)$$

Using Eq. (3.23) the i^{th} element of $J_{p,m}$ can be calculated by the following expression:

$$\frac{\partial \varepsilon_{p,m}}{\partial w_i} = \sum_{k=1}^p \frac{\partial Y_{k,m}}{\partial w_i} \equiv \sum_{k=1}^p j_{p,k,i} \quad (3.26)$$

Where the $j_{p,k,i}$ values can be calculated by:

$$j_{p,k,Yp(j,i)} = \delta_{Y_{k,i}} y_{IY(j,i)} \quad (3.27)$$

$$j_{p,k,Xp(j,i)} = \delta_{Y_{k,j}} \begin{cases} d_{pC(p)-\Delta(i)} & \text{if } i \leq no \\ x_{pC(p)-\Delta(i)} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3.28)$$

$$j_{p,k,Bp(j)} = \delta_{Y_{k,j}} \quad (3.29)$$

Where the δ parameter can be calculated by the following expressions:

$$\delta_{j,j} = f'_j(\text{net}_j) \quad (3.30)$$

$$\delta_{j,i} = \delta_{j,j} \sum_{k=i}^{j-1} \begin{cases} w_{Wp(j,k)} \delta_{k,i} & Wp(j,k) \neq 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

The quasi-Hessian can be denoted by:

$$Q_{p,m} = J_{p,m}^T J_{p,m} \quad (3.31)$$

With the abovementioned equations, the weight update can be calculated by the algorithm presented in **Figure 3.9**.

```

% Initialisation
g = 0
Q = 0
for p = 1 to no
  for all neurons (n)
    calculate net; % Eq. (3.20)
    calculate y; % Eq. (2.13)
    calculate  $\delta$ ; % Eq. (3.30)
  end;
  for k=1 to no
    for j = 1 to n
      for i = 1 to IY(j)
        calculate  $jp,k,Yp(j,i)$  %Eq. (3.27)
      end;
      for i = 1 to IX(j)
        calculate  $jp,k,Xp(j,i)$  %Eq. (3.28)
      end;
       $jp,k,Bp(j)$  %Eq. (3.28)
    end;
  end;
  calculate Jacobian; % Eq. (3.25-3.26)
  calculate gradient % Eq. (3.24)
end;
calculate  $w^*$  % Eq. (3.23)

```

Figure 3.9. Pseudo-code of the updated weights using the improved accumulative NBN algorithm

3.4 Results and discussions

The prediction results obtained by the application of the ANN and the improved NBN training algorithm explained above are presented, analysed and discussed in this section.

Using the simulation procedures discussed in **section 2.2**, a dataset was generated that contains 6323 degradation points (patterns) for a single mechanical component; and this data is used as a training dataset, as depicted in **Figure 2.6**. Using the same simulation procedures, an expected degradation path beyond the training dataset was also generated (extrapolation of the expected degradation path) up to 0.35 degradation level to reach the next failure, as seen in **Figure 3.10**. This dataset (purple in **Figure 3.10**) is used for model testing as the extrapolated degradation path, then the degradation path is predicted accordingly along with the failure, and finally, the RUL is estimated.

Figure 3.10. Extrapolated expected degradation path

The prediction algorithm was developed based on the improved NBN training algorithm and coded using the Wolfram Mathematica software package. Referring to the developed network design in **Figure 3.8** and **Figure 3.11**, the bipolar hyperbolic tangent (\tanh) was used as the activation function for the hidden layers and between neurons, while any non-linear activation function which ensures that the output is monotonously increased could be used for the output neurons (i.e., $f(x) = x^2$).

3.4.1 Prediction model characteristics

The summary of the training process results is presented in **Table 3.1**.

Table 3.1. Summary of the training process results

Hidden layers activation function	tanh
Output activation function	Non-linear ($f \in \mathbb{R}^+$); ($f(x) = x^2$)
No. neurons	3
Training algorithm	NBN-forward-only
Error function	Root mean squared error (RMSE)
No. iterations	578 (545)
RMSE Training	0.000911
RMSE testing	0.005283
Avg RMSE	0.007196

In **Figure 3.11-A** An example of the improved accumulative ANN-NBN network architecture is displayed, while **Figure 3.11-B** shows an example of the original ANN-NBN network architecture.

Figure 3.11. Example of training model network architectures 4 inputs and 1 final output: A) NBN-accumulative neural network; B) NBN-original neural network

The orange nodes are the input nodes of the network, while the pink nodes are the outputs. In **Figure 3.11-A**, the time window is illustrated (the output of node 7 at the time 't' is $Y(t)$, the input of node 1 is $Y(t-1)$, the input of node 2 is $Y(t-2)$, the input of node 3 is $Y(t-3)$ and so on. **Figure 3.12** depicts the training curve of the prediction model, where the training took about 578 iterations to achieve the minimum training error.

Figure 3.12. Training curve of the developed improved ANN-NBN model

3.4.2 Prognostic analysis - Failure prediction and RUL estimation

For the given training dataset, the developed improved ANN-NBN model is trained to predict the degradation path for each failure cycle and predict future failure, as seen in **Figure 3.13**.

Since the failure threshold of 0.3 is already predefined for the whole training and testing datasets, the failure is labelled for the entire dataset and ready for implementing the supervised learning approach. The simulated testing dataset of the expected degradation path discussed above (**Figure 3.10**) was used for testing the failure prediction.

Figure 3.13. Degradation path and failure prediction

The grey highlighted area in **Figure 3.13** represents the prediction process starting from the last training point until the end of the prediction of the expected degradation path (testing dataset); once the predicted path crosses the predefined threshold, failure occurs (green point); replacement of the failed component is required.

For the calculation of the RUL, the failure point (ft) is subtracted from the last training point. **Figure 3.14** magnifies the prediction process area (the grey area in **Figure 3.13**). As seen in **Figure 3.14**, two RULs can be defined: RUL_{ANN} is the predicted RUL by the developed ANN model, while RUL_e is the expected RUL based on the expected degradation path of the testing dataset. The RUL_{ANN} can be estimated by subtracting the last training point from the predicted failure point (ft_{ANN}), while the RUL_e can be estimated by subtracting the last training point from the expected failure point (ft_e) of the testing data.

Figure 3.14. Magnification of the prediction process area for RUL estimation

The RUL_{ANN} of the mechanical component is approximately equal to 197, while the RUL_e is approximately equal to 192.

The performance of the developed model was tested using the RMSE performance index. The RMSE of the training dataset is 0.000911, while for the testing dataset, the RMSE is 0.005283. The difference between the two RMSE values indicates the small training error and the high correlation between the trained and predicted data, thus an acceptable performance of the trained model.

To compare the RUL prediction accuracy of the improved accumulative NBN-ANN model with the original NBN-ANN model, an experiment of 1000 epoch runs for both was conducted.

Table 3.2 shows the experimental parameters, knowing that, all parameters are fixed for all runs except the maximum training error.

Table 3.2. The experimental parameters of the RUL prediction accuracy analysis – Accumulative NBN vs Original NBN

Total runs / epochs	1000
Filter size (points)	11
Predefined failure threshold	0.3
Max training error (Accumulative ANN-NBN)	0.00001
Max training error (Original ANN-NBN)	0.0007
Last training point	6323

The RUL_{ANN} and RUL_e of the mechanical component were estimated for each run and then the prediction error was calculated using Eq. (2.8).

The experimental results are summarised in **Table 3.3** below.

Table 3.3. Summary of the experimental results – Accumulative NBN-ANN vs Original NBN-ANN

Item	Results	
	Accumulative NBN-ANN	Original NBN-ANN
Total run time (1000 epochs)	~10 hours	~3.5 hours
Prediction RMSE	8.857 (time in sampling period)	11.992 (time in sampling period)
Prediction success rate	100%	97.6%

The results show that the improved accumulative NBN-ANN outperforms the original NBN-ANN in terms of the prediction error (less prediction error means more prediction accuracy), and its prediction success rate is 100% compared to the 97.6% of the original one.

The prediction success rate means the number of runs the prediction algorithm succeeded in predicting the failure crossing the predefined threshold of 0.3, then estimating the RUL. The NBN-accumulative neural network was successful in the prediction at all runs. At the same time, the original NBN-ANN failed to predict the failure and estimate the RUL 24 times through the overall runs.

Figure 3.15 shows sample cases of the failed predictions of the original NBN-ANN, where the predicted paths could not exceed the predefined failure threshold of 0.3.

Figure 3.15. Sample cases of failed predictions – original NBN-ANN

3.4.3 Model Validation using real degradation data

The developed improved NBN-accumulative neural network model was validated using the NASA Ames milling dataset [213]. The performance of the trained model was validated using the cross-validation technique in a standardised manner.

The data in the NASA Ames milling dataset resulted from tests performed on a milling machine under different operating conditions, covering sixteen cases with different number of runs. Sample of the dataset is presented in **Table 3.4**. The experimental measurements included the tool wear parameter (flank wear - VB) which was measured for each run using a microscope as the distance from the cutting edge to the end of the abrasive wear of the flank face of the tool, time, depth of cut, feed, and material. Four settings were used in the cutting experiment, with depth of cut of 1.5 and 0.75 mm and feed rates of 0.5 and 0.25 mm/rev.

Table 3.4. NASA Ames milling dataset – sample data

Case	VB	Time	DOC	feed	material
1	0	0	0	0	1
1	0	2	1.5	0.5	2
1	0.11	5	1.5	0.5	1
1	0.2	8	1.5	0.5	1
1	0.24	4	1.5	0.5	2
1	0.29	3	1.5	0.5	2
1	0.28	4	1.5	0.5	1
1	0.29	3	1.5	0.5	1

A sample of one case of data is presented in **Figure 3.16**.

Figure 3.16 Tool wear over time - a sample case of the NASA milling dataset [213]

To pre-process the original dataset for the model validation, empty values of VB were removed and zero value was added after the final run for each case to indicate the tool replacement action.

Using the milling dataset, 15 test runs were performed using a standard cross-validation test based on the root mean squared error (RMSE) performance index. For each run, 15 cases were used for training and the remaining one case for validation. The cross-validation test was conducted twice to check the ability of the model to predict the real degradation data (flank wear) including complex relationships (4 inputs), and to compare the degradation prediction results with a similar published study conducted by Cai et al. [211] in which one input only (depth of cut) was used from the same dataset to predict the flank wear using two ANN-MLP models.

Table 3.5 shows the performance index results of the conducted cross-validation tests.

Table 3.5. Cross-validation performance index results of each case - NASA Ames milling dataset

	Test 1: 4 inputs	Test 2: 1 input
Case	RMSE	RMSE
1	0.044144	0.040406
2	0.010399	0.06697
3	0.013336	0.06319
4	0.011552	0.009224
5	0.02915	0.023862
7	0.006948	0.015816
8	0.016162	0.031203
9	0.025767	0.019373
10	0.010106	0.046464
11	0.038917	0.24454
12	0.027711	0.01135
13	0.106338	0.085416
14	0.019475	0.061296
15	0.055474	0.032235
16	0.019157	0.025088
RMSE Avg	0.028976	0.051762

From **Table 3.5**, it can be seen that the improved accumulative NBN-ANN model was able to predict the flank wear based on both four inputs (time, depth of cut, feed rate and material) and one input (depth of cut), producing good performance results with an average RMSE= 0.028976 and 0.051762 of the four input models and the one input model, respectively and for all cases.

It can be concluded that the developed fault prognostics method based on the improved accumulative ANN-NBN training algorithm is able to train models of real degradation data (flank wear) with multi covariates with an acceptable error.

Moreover, the validation results using the developed model achieved better average error of 0.051762 RMSE compared to the achieved average error in the previously mentioned study of 0.2137 and 0.2168 RMSE.

3.5 Summary

The NBN training algorithm was improved to increase the ability to maintain the monotonously increasing trend of the degradation process of mechanical components. The improvements included a data filtering process in addition to a new design of the ANN using accumulative network structure along with FCN and ACN architectures and specific types of activation functions. A simulated labelled degradation dataset of a mechanical component with a predefined failure threshold was exploited for verification. Supervised machine learning models, including combined artificial neural network architectures, an improved version of the neuron-by-neuron training algorithm and a unique neural network design, were applied for the prediction process.

The results show that the used approach is efficient in predicting failure and estimating the RUL of mechanical components with high accuracy and a high prediction success rate. Moreover, the model showed its ability to predict real degradation data using the NASA Ames milling dataset and achieved good results compared to a published similar study.

Chapter 4.

COMPARISON OF ML-BASED DEGRADATION PATH PREDICTION AND FAULT PROGNOSTICS MODELS

4.1 Introduction

Different data-driven or ML models can be used for failure prediction; such as support vector machines (SVM), random forests, logistic regression, artificial neural networks (ANN), Naive Bayes, genetic algorithms, Neuro-Fuzzy systems, support vector regression (SVR) and other methods have all been utilised in machine learning to predict failures and detect anomalies [56], [57], [58], [59], [60], [62], [214]. Different models' structures, network architectures and other parameters can be optimised to get the best prediction results.

This chapter provides the development procedures and discusses the results of developing different ML models, investigating their prediction abilities and comparing their performances. The models are developed based on different types of ML algorithms, such as ANN, Support vector machines (SVM), Random Forest (RF), Regressions and autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA). Model development can also contain different structures and network designs, such as using various training functions, activation functions, number of neurons and hidden layers and network architectures. The analysis was performed in terms of different aspects, such as degradation path prediction, failure and RUL prediction, and the models' ability to handle multiple mechanical components and different degradation laws.

The selected network architecture strongly affects the training success [215]; the use of the NBN algorithm could solve the problem of the inability to handle other types of architectures rather than the most common MLP, such as BMLP (Bridged multi-layer perceptron), FCN, ACN and multi-layer perceptron with linear neurons (MLPL) [175].

4.2 Methodology

The proposed methodology to conduct different experiments to evaluate and investigate the different fault prognostic models is depicted in **Figure 4.1**.

Figure 4.1. Flowchart of the evaluation and comparison methodology of fault prognostics models

The methodology is described as follows:

1. Degradation data simulation: For models verification purposes, the required degradation data is simulated to be used for training and testing the developed models, as discussed in **section 2.2**.
2. Data pre-processing: The mechanical component's degradation dataset is prepared for the training and testing phases.
3. ML models selection, network and structures design, coding, training and testing: Different network designs, activation functions, training

algorithms and related parameters are selected and processed to train and evaluate the intended models.

4. Prediction outputs: The trained models give predictions for the degradation path, failure time and RUL.
5. ML models investigation and evaluation: The developed models are compared according to their performance and prediction accuracy. Prediction results in terms of each prediction output are discussed, the ability of each model to predict the required output is investigated, and then a comparative analysis is performed accordingly.

4.3 Results and discussions

4.3.1 Degradation path prediction using different models, structures and architectures of ANN

This section presents the application of the “Neuron-by-Neuron (NBN)” training algorithm with forward-backward computation to predict the degradation path of a machine component leading to failure and replacement. Different models with various architectures of artificial neural networks, mainly fully connected networks (FCN) and arbitrarily connected networks (ACN), have been developed to predict the degradation path within the available range of the given data set. It is the first step towards predicting the degradation and failure data and developing a predictive maintenance framework. In the next step, the prediction results can be used to conduct simulations for better maintenance planning and scheduling.

The NBN training algorithm with forward-backward computations has been used to predict the degradation levels of a mechanical component. Based on the NBN routings, this makes the algorithm suitable for ACNs and offers a proper method to be used for modelling the tremendous amount of data provided by the complex machines of complex manufacturing systems.

Different numbers of neurons and two types of network architectures (FCN and ACN) were used to model and predict the degradation path.

Table 4.1 shows the used topologies and architectures for the developed models.

Table 4.1. Topologies and architectures of the developed models

Model no.	1	2	3
Network design	FCN	FCN	FCN
Topology	n 2 mbip 1 n 3 mbip 1 2 n 4 mlin 1 2 3	n 2 mbip 1 n 3 mbip 1 2 n 4 mbip 1 2 3 n 5 mbip 1 2 3 4 n 6 mlin 1 2 3 4 5	n 2 mbip 1 n 3 mbip 1 2 n 4 mbip 1 2 3 n 5 mbip 1 2 3 4 n 6 mbip 1 2 3 4 5 n 7 mbip 1 2 3 4 5 6 n 8 mbip 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 n 9 mlin 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
ANN architecture			
Model no.	4	5	6
Network design	ACN	ACN	ACN
Topology	n 2 mbip 1 n 3 mbip 1 2 n 4 mbip 1 2 3 n 5 mbip 1 2 3 n 6 mbip 1 2 3 4 5 n 7 mbip 1 2 3 4 5 6 n 8 mbip 1 2 3 4 5 6 n 9 mlin 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8	n 2 mbip 1 n 3 mbip 1 2 n 4 mbip 1 2 3 n 5 mbip 1 2 3 n 6 mlin 1 2 3 4 5	n 2 mbip 1 n 3 mbip 1 n 4 mlin 1 2 3
ANN architecture			

The neural networks are initialised with random weights in the range of -1 to 1. The used activation function for hidden layers (used by neurons) is bipolar hyperbolic tangent (tanh) activation function symbolised as “mbip”, knowing that bipolar neurons have positive or negative outputs. Likewise, the linear activation function “mlin” is used for the output neurons, where linear activation functions

are used if the desired output is larger than zero [216]. The output of neuron j presented in Eq. (2.13) is defined as:

$$y_j = f_j(\text{gain} \times \text{net}_j) + \text{der} \times \text{net}_j \quad (4.1)$$

The “gain” and “der” are parameters of the activation functions. The parameter “der” is introduced to adjust the slope of the activation function, where the slope is approaching zero [216]. These parameters are set to be gain=0.50 and der=0.01 for the “mbip” neurons, while gain=1.00 and der=0.01 for the “mlin” neurons.

Table 4.2 shows the summary of the conducted experiments with the six ANN models presented in **Table 4.1** to predict the degradation path of the component.

Table 4.2. Summary of the “training and testing” processes of the various degradation path prediction ANN models

Model number	ANN models					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Network architecture	FCN	FCN	FCN	ACN	ACN	ACN
Hidden layers activation function	mbip (tanh)					
Output activation function	Mlin (linear)					
No. neurons	3	5	8	8	5	3
Training algorithm	NBN-forward backward					
No. patterns /overall dataset	6323					
No. patterns / training (80%)	5058					
No. patterns / test (20%)	1265					
Error function	Root mean squared error (RMSE)					
RMSE / training	0.000826	0.001347	0.000769	0.000744	0.000961	0.000635
RMSE / test	0.000857	0.001343	0.000894	0.00081	0.000928	0.000659

The adequacy of the ANN models is validated using the RMSE performance measure. The selected best-trained models are those with the least RMSE. According to **Table 4.2** and **Error! Reference source not found.**, model no. 3 (8 neurons - FCN) and model no. 6 (3 neurons - ACN) are the best-trained models.

The NBN algorithm was able to train the network to a small error $\text{RMSE}_{\text{Training}} = 0.000769$ and 0.000635 for FCN and ACN, respectively. The testing results are acceptable with $\text{RMSE}_{\text{Test}} = 0.000894$ and 0.000659 for FCN and ACN, respectively.

Figure 4.2 shows the training curve of the best two models.

Figure 4.2. Training curve of the best-trained degradation path prediction models

Table 4.3 shows the training results: the prediction success rate, which can be defined as the number of successful predictions of the failure point when the degradation crosses the predefined threshold, the average number of iterations and the average time. From **Table 4.2** and **Table 4.3**, it can be seen that the used NBN training algorithm is able to successfully train both FCN and ACN architectures and achieve significant results (low prediction error) with a fewer number of neurons and iterations.

Table 4.3. Training results

No. neurons	Success rate (%)		Avg no. iterations		Avg time (s)	
	FCN	ACN	FCN	ACN	FCN	ACN
3	100	100	255	207	0.62	9.22
5	100	100	214	209	6.45	13.11
8	100	100	222	228	34.86	35.49

Figure 4.3 shows a sample of the degradation path prediction results of model 3 (e.i., FCN, 8 neurons). It can be noticed that there is a high correlation between the target and the predicted values in the testing dataset due to the small prediction error.

Figure 4.3. Degradation path prediction / Model no. 3

4.3.2 Failure prediction using different ANN and other data-driven models

A comparative analysis of the main characteristics of different artificial neural network approaches used to predict failures in mechanical components is presented in this section. The comparative analysis is based on various key parameters, such as network architecture, training algorithm, output activation function and computation method.

For failure prediction, the simulated degradation dataset discussed in **section 2.2** was used with a predefined failure threshold considered a Health Indicator (HI) of the mechanical component being studied.

Seven ANN models (ANN 1 – ANN 7), as presented in **Table 4.4** and **Table 4.5**, were developed with different key parameters. The comparisons are made based on investigating the effect of changing such key parameters on performance indicators, such as prediction accuracy, prediction error and prediction success rate. **Table 4.4** summarises the architectures and training algorithms used for the prediction models.

Table 4.4. Summary of the used ANN architectures and training algorithms for the developed failure prediction models

ANN Model	Architecture	Training algorithm/computations method
ANN 1	MLP 1-10-1	Radial basis function (RBF) – forward-backward
ANN 2	MLP 1-2-1	Gradient descent (GD) – forward-backward
ANN 3 (3 variants)	MLP 1-3-1, MLP 1-2-2-2-1, MLP 1-3-3-1	EBP – forward-backward
ANN 4	MLP 1-3-1	LM – forward-backward
ANN 5	FCN	NBN – forward-backward
ANN 6	FCN	NBN – forward-only
ANN 7	FCN	NBN – accumulative forward-only

The training summary and results of the developed models are presented in **Table 4.5**.

Table 4.5. Prediction results and training summary of 100 runs

	ANN 1	ANN 2	ANN 3	ANN 4	ANN 5	ANN 6	ANN 7
Number of neurons	10	2	3, 6, 6	3	3	3	3
Hidden layers activation function	Softmax	tanh					
Outputs activation function	Identity	Identity	Linear	tanh	tanh	tanh	Non-linear ($f \in \mathbb{R}^+$); ($f(x) = x^2$)
RMSE Training	0.061876	0.012385	***	0.000389	0.000365	0.000658	0.000911
RMSE Testing (prediction accuracy)	0.205641	0.040704	***	0.001172	0.00112	0.002065	0.005283
Failure prediction error	+42	+3	***	+1	+1	-9	-2
Predicted failure point	6559	6520	***	6518	6518	6526	6515
Expected failure point	6517						
Prediction success rate	62%	80%	***	91%	94%	97.6%	100%

The MLP architecture was used along with different training algorithms, such as RBF, GD, LM, and EBP, with the traditional forward-backward computations to design the first four models. The last three models have FCN architecture (and are able to have ACN architecture as well) with the NBN training algorithm. The NBN is the only algorithm that can deal with such types of structures. Unlike the other training algorithms, using the NBN algorithm, forward-backward or forward-only computations can be employed for the training and prediction processes. ANN 7 is the model discussed in detail in **section 3.3**.

Different commonly used linear and non-linear activation functions were used. Root mean squared error (RMSE) was used as the performance metric. All models

achieved very low training and testing error; thus, the performance of the developed models can be considered reasonable for the failure prediction of the mechanical component, except for the EBP (ANN 3). When investigating the EBP training algorithm, different numbers of neurons (i.e., 3 and 6 neurons) along with different MLP structures (1-3-1, 1-2-2-2-1 and 1-3-3-1) were used; however, it was not possible to train these model variants with our dataset or make predictions (the training process in all cases resulted in a very high-performance error and the models failed to predict the failure).

The failure prediction results for each of the six models that succeeded in the prediction are presented below. It can be seen from the failure prediction results illustrated in **Table 4.5** and in

Figure 4.4, **Figure 4.5** and **Figure 4.6** that the six models were able to predict the failure around the expected failure point (6517). Model (ANN 7) succeeded in predicting the failure point prior to the expected failure point (i.e., point 6517) with the lowest prediction error of -2.

Figure 4.4. Failure prediction results: **A:** ANN 4. MLP+LM and **B:** ANN 2. MLP+GD

Figure 4.5. Failure prediction result: **A:** ANN 5. FCN+NBN-forward-backward and **B:** ANN 1. MLP+RBF

Figure 4.6. Failure prediction results: **A:** ANN 6. FCN+NBN-forward-only, and **B:** ANN 7. FCN+NBN-accumulative forward-only

All models have a relatively high prediction success rate except the ANN 1, while the best one is ANN 7 (Accumulative NBN) with 100% success rate. Overall, rather than the very close training and testing errors of all developed models, the accumulative NBN model (ANN 7) outperformed the other models regarding failure prediction success rate and produced a small prediction error, slightly larger than some of the other models.

The predictions were made based on the extrapolated predicted degradation path. The six models can predict failure but with different constraints. In terms of the training error, the LM and NBN gave the best performance due to their low errors. It can be concluded that the best ANN model to predict the failure of mechanical components is the NBN algorithm combined with FCN architecture.

A brief comparison of the used ANN architectures in the developed models is summarised in **Table 4.6**, based on some prediction factors/ constraints.

Table 4.6. Comparison of the used ANN architectures

	FCN / ACN	MLP
Prediction accuracy	High	Moderate
Training/ prediction time	Short	Longer
Convergence speed	Fast	Slow
Number of neurons	Less	More
Memory consumption	Low	High
Required programming skills	High	Moderate
Size of input patterns	Huge (infinite)	Small-medium
Structure complexity	High (including arbitrarily connected structures)	Moderate
Computation methods	Forward-backward / Forward-only	Forward-backward

To verify the effectiveness of the developed improved accumulative ANN-NBN model (ANN 7), the prediction results were compared with other commonly used data-driven (ML) models, such as non-linear regression (logistic function), random forest (RF), support vector machines (SVM), and time series models, such as autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) and its special case “exponential smoothing”. The software tools used for developing such models were STATISTICA and SPSS. **Table 4.7** shows the prediction results of each model, while **Figure 4.7** summarises the performance (RMSE) of these models together with the improved accumulative ANN-NBN (ANN 7).

Table 4.7. Summary of the experimental results of other data-driven models

Model performance	Data-driven models	
	Non-linear Regression (logistic)	Random forest (RF – 100 trees)
RMSE (Training)	0.00229	0.03399
RMSE (Testing)	0.00678	0.12622
Summary / model performance	Data-driven SVM models	
	SVM I	SVM II
SVM type	Regression type I	
Kernel type	Radial Basis Function (RBF)	Polynomial
SVs	525 (478 bounded)	590 (582 bounded)
RMSE (Training)	0.14096	0.18041
RMSE (Testing)	0.37552	0.46856
Model performance	Data-driven models	
	Exponential smoothing	ARIMA (0,0,1)
RMSE	0.01374	0.01374

Table 4.7 and **Figure 4.7** show that the improved accumulative ANN-NBN model (ANN 7) achieved the best training error, thus, the highest prediction accuracy over the other developed models. While the ARIMA (0,0,1) and exponential smoothing models achieved relatively higher errors than the non-linear regression (logistic function) and the accumulative ANN-NBN models, the RF and SVM models produced much higher errors.

Figure 4.7. Performance metric (RMSE training) comparisons of the developed models

4.3.3 Model evaluation of different degradation laws

A test was conducted to evaluate the developed improved accumulative ANN-NBN prediction model for multiple components having different degradation laws. All the investigated components have different degradation models that are described by the following mean degradation function:

$$m(t, q) = t^q \tag{4.2}$$

q was randomly selected for each component in the following intervals: $2 \pm \frac{\text{Range}}{2}$, where “Range” goes from 0 to 0.6 in uniform steps. For each Range value, 20 tests were carried out. Figure 4.8 and Figure 4.9 show the test results; the same range value has the same colour. In each test, 10 degradation curves (10 components) were used for the training and 1 for testing.

The absolute and relative errors were calculated according to Eq. (2.9) and Eq. (2.10) for each test and summarised in Figure 4.8 and Figure 4.9, respectively. The solid line shows the average error for a given range value.

Figure 4.8. Multiple components test results – Absolute error

Figure 4.9. Multiple components test results – Relative error

The test results indicate the effectiveness of the improved accumulative ANN-NBN prediction model in the case of multiple components having different degradation laws.

4.4 Summary

The degradation path prediction results show that the used networks are successfully able to predict the degradation path; the 8-neurons model of FCN architecture and the 3-neurons model of ACN architecture with tanh hidden layers activation function and a linear function of the outputs have the lowest prediction error (RMSE) among all the developed models. The results confirmed that, in general, the improved accumulative ANN-NBN algorithm outperforms the other prediction models in terms of prediction success rate and prediction accuracy. In addition, the improved accumulative ANN-NBN algorithm showed its ability to handle the degradation prediction of multiple mechanical components with different degradation laws.

Chapter 5.

PROBABILISTIC ANN MODEL FOR RELIABILITY ANALYSIS AND LIFE DEGRADATION ESTIMATION

5.1 Introduction

Manufacturers have been paying attention to maintaining and improving the system's reliability (R) and availability using different strategies, e.g., PdM, by utilising different ML techniques, e.g., ANN, for failure and RUL prediction and reliability model estimation [188]. This chapter presents an ANN-based probabilistic method that can predict the successive values of the multi-cycle degradation process along with a preventive replacement strategy and model the degradation path of a mechanical component by estimating the parameters of the probability model and the reliability.

5.2 Methodology

To estimate the component's reliability and its life degradation at any time horizon, in the case of a successive degradation points law, a probabilistic life degradation estimation method is proposed, as depicted in **Figure 5.1**.

The proposed method includes several steps that can be summarised as the following:

1. Degradation data (measurements): The needed input degradation measurements are acquired from real or experimental sources. For verification purposes in this study, these data are simulated based on specific degradation laws.
2. Data pre-processing: The required data are prepared for the training process. When there are multiple input features, the features selection method is applied to include the most influential ones (in our case, we have only one input feature, which is the degradation time step in which the replacement occurs). Additionally, a failure threshold is defined for the degradation data, and if necessary, the dataset values are normalised. Then, the training and testing datasets are ready for the prediction process.

3. New ANN probabilistic model development and training: The probabilistic model to estimate the life degradation and the components' reliability is designed and trained. The maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) method is implemented, where the NBN training algorithm is used to calculate the gradient in an efficient way, while the likelihood is maximised using the BFGS (Broyden, Fletcher, Goldfarb, Shanno) algorithm. The prediction process aims to estimate the distribution parameters of the degradation data at any successive time horizon of the extrapolated expected degradation path.
4. The error acceptance criteria are the same as the ones discussed in section 3.2.

These steps are discussed in detail in section 5.3.

Figure 5.1. The proposed methodology flowchart

5.3 Results and discussions

The degradation measurements of a mechanical component for the probabilistic model were simulated according to the methodology discussed in **section 2.2**. A sample of the degradation data for a specific time horizon is depicted in **Figure 5.2**.

Figure 5.2. A sample of degradation measurements

It is assumed that perfect maintenance action is carried out when the failure occurs (degradation path crosses the predefined failure threshold); thus, the component is replaced, and a new cycle is initiated.

5.3.1 ANN probabilistic model development and prediction results

The development of the probabilistic ANN model was carried out in a joint research project. The model is described in detail in the **APPENDIX**.

The ANN model was developed and coded using the Wolfram Mathematica software package. The NBN training algorithm with forward-only computations was used to train the model along with two potential types of network architectures; mainly fully connected network (FCN) and arbitrarily connected network (ACN).

Table 5.1 presents the proposed topology of the probabilistic ANN model, and **Figure 5.3** depicts the proposed network design for the case when there are three inputs and two outputs of the network. One of the inputs, $X(p)$, is the time starting when the component is new or replaced as a new; “ p ” denotes the actual time step. The two outputs of the network, $Y1(p)1$ and $Y1(p)2$, are the two predicted

parameters of the distribution function. If it is the normal distribution, these are the mean and the variance. Using these two parameters, the expected value (E) of the degradation is calculated. The two previous degradation values predicted in time steps $p-1$ and $p-2$ are also processed by the ANN as two further inputs.

The MLE method was used to estimate the distribution parameters θ of the degradation data by selecting the weights of the ANN neurons w , which maximise the likelihood or minimise the negative likelihood using the BFGS algorithm.

Table 5.1. ANN proposed network topology - FCN: 1 input, 2 hidden layers, 2 outputs

	Network neurons index	Activation function	Input layer patterns connections	First hidden layer connections		Second hidden layer connections	
First hidden layer neurons	N1	tanh	$X(p)$				
	N2		$X(p)$				
Second hidden layer neurons	N3	tanh	$X(p)$	1	2		
	N4		$X(p)$	1	2		
Outputs	N5	Quadratic	$X(p)$	1	2	3	4
	N6		$X(p)$	1	2	3	4

Figure 5.3. Proposed ANN design – FCN: 1 input, 2 hidden layers, 2 outputs
The summary of the training process results is presented in **Table 5.2.**

Table 5.2. Summary of the developed model

Hidden layers activation function	tanh
Output activation function	Quadratic
No. neurons in the hidden layers	4
No. hidden layers	2
No. outputs	2
Training algorithm	NBN
Computations method	forward-only
Cost function	-log-likelihood
No. iterations	336
Optimised objective function	-195.718
Parameters estimation method	MLE
Optimisation algorithm	BFGS

Figure 5.4 depicts the training curve of the developed model, where the training took about 336 iterations and the minimum -log-likelihood was -195.718.

Figure 5.4. Training curve of the developed probabilistic ANN model

The developed probabilistic ANN model was trained to predict the life degradation for each successive degradation point of different failure cycles; **Figure 5.5** shows an example of the prediction outputs of the model.

Figure 5.5. Sample of the model output for training and prediction data: Probabilistic degradation estimation of multi-replacement cycles

The proposed model was also designed and trained to predict the successive degradation for some future points, as seen by the “pink” region curve of in **Figure 5.5**. Furthermore, it can be noticed that the failure probability increases as the mean degradation increases over time (get closer to the predefined failure threshold); hence the reliability of each degradation point decreases. Moreover, the variance of the degradation points becomes larger as time increases.

5.3.2 Monte Carlo simulation-based optimisation of preventive maintenance

For performance analysis by comparing the results of the ANN model with the theoretical calculations, Monte Carlo (MC) simulations were performed to simulate two numerical examples of preventive maintenance (PM) optimisation; namely “ANN” and “theoretical”. **Table 5.3** summarises the main MC simulation assumptions.

Table 5.3. Summary of the assumptions of MC simulation

Number of simulations	10000
Cost PM	1
Cost Fail	3 times the cost PM

“ANN” indicates that the degradation distribution parameters were estimated with the use of the ANN model presented above, and using these parameters, the failure probability ($P_{fail ANN}$) and the cumulative distribution function of failure

time (CDF_{ANN}) during the simulation were calculated. While for the “theoretical” calculations, the failure probability ($P_{fail\ Theoretical}$) and the cumulative distribution function of failure time ($CDF_{Theoretical}$) were calculated based on the gamma-process degradation model. Suppose that the predefined failure threshold is $h = 0.3$, then ($D_0 = 0.3$), and the degradation level is $\mathbf{Var}(D(t)) = \sigma^2 m(t)$, where σ is the variance and $m(t)$ is the mean of the degradation of the component.

Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{Var}(D(t)) &= \sigma^2 m(t), \quad D_0 < 0.3 \quad \text{No failure} \\ \mathbf{Var}(D(t)) &= 0, \quad D_0 \geq 0.3 \quad \text{Failure occurs} \end{aligned} \tag{5.1}$$

The failure time (ft) is counted once the degradation path crosses the failure threshold, as indicated in **Figure 5.6**, and then the component is replaced.

Figure 5.6. Predicted failure time

From both cases, i.e., the ANN probabilistic model and the theoretical calculations, the failure probabilities ($P_{fail\ ANN}$ and $P_{fail\ Theoretical}$) and other indicators, such as the failure cumulative density function (CDF) and reliability, are estimated based on the extrapolated expected degradation path. The most common reason for using a preventive replacement strategy is to reduce the long-term maintenance cost per unit of time. The expected cycle length for a component that is replaced either at the time it fails or at the scheduled maintenance interval x is [217]:

$$E(\text{Cycle Length}) = \int_0^x t \cdot f(t)dt + R(x)x = \int_0^x R(t)dt \tag{5.2}$$

The expected cost for one cycle is:

$$E(\text{Cost Per Cycle}) = C_p R(x) + C_U(1 - R(x)) \tag{5.3}$$

Thus, the expected long-term cost per unit time is:

$$CPUT(x) = \frac{E(\text{Cost Per Cycle})}{E(\text{Cycle Length})} = \frac{C_p R(x) + C_u(1 - R(x))}{\int_0^x R(t)dt} \tag{5.4}$$

The value of x that minimises the $CPUT$ is the ideal preventive maintenance interval.

In Eq. (5.2-5.4):

- $f(t)$ is the probability density function (PDF) of the failure time
- $R(t)$ is the reliability function of the failure time
- C_p is the average cost due to a planned maintenance
- C_u is the average cost due to an unplanned maintenance

Figure 5.7 shows the PDF and the CDF of the preventive maintenance (PM) numerical example of some PM time units predicted based on the extrapolated expected degradation path; the PM aims at estimating the optimal preventive maintenance time, the minimised cost per unit time and the reliability from both outputs of the developed ANN model and the theoretical calculations. It is shown that the mean of the estimated PM failure times by the ANN models is 114.7, while the theoretically calculated mean is equal to 114.6 which are very close to each other. The standard deviation of the estimated PM failure times is 0.6916, and of the theoretically calculated equal to 1.0644.

Figure 5.7. PDF and CDF of failure times calculated theoretically and estimated by developed probabilistic ANN model

Figure 5.8 shows the achieved minimum cost per unit time of the preventive maintenance obtained theoretically, which equal to 0.095585 and estimated by the developed probabilistic ANN model which equal to 0.083438. The expected value of the optimal PM cycle time is estimated theoretically equal to 111.99, while using the ANN model equal to 112.91. The optimal PM estimation results of the ANN model are very close to the theoretical estimations with a small relative error of 0.82%.

Figure 5.8. Comparison of the achieved cost per unit time calculated theoretically and estimated by the developed probabilistic ANN model

It can be noticed that the developed probabilistic ANN model achieved close results to the theoretical calculation in terms of the main objective function of the preventive replacement maintenance strategy of minimising the expected long-term cost per unit time and estimating the optimal PM cycle time.

Figure 5.9 depicts a comparison between the theoretically calculated reliability of the component and the estimated reliability by the probabilistic ANN model over a time horizon.

Figure 5.9. Comparison of plot reliability degradation over time – calculated theoretically and estimated by the developed probabilistic ANN model

It can be seen in **Figure 5.9** that the developed probabilistic ANN model estimates that the reliability (R) of the component is close to the theoretically calculated.

The performance metrics of the developed probabilistic ANN model presented above are calculated based on Eq. (2.11, 2.12) and summarised in **Table 5.4** below.

Table 5.4. Summary of the performance metrics of the developed probabilistic ANN model

Performance metric	Cost per unit time	Reliability (R)
RMSE	0.0111	0.0759
R^2	0.9520	0.9750

Table 5.4 shows that the performance metrics resulted in a relatively small error between the achieved cost per unit time and the estimated reliability from the developed probabilistic ANN model compared to the theoretical calculations. The coefficient of determination R^2 The model is more than 95% in both cases, indicating that the model is good.

5.4 Summary

In this section, a probabilistic degradation prediction method has been presented. This method was developed in a joint research project. The method can predict the successive values of the degradation path of a mechanical component that follows a perfect maintenance replacement strategy. The method includes a unique ANN design and training algorithm, and the maximum likelihood estimation method (MLE) is implemented to estimate the distribution parameters exploiting the BFGS (Broyden, Fletcher, Goldfarb, Shanno) second-order optimisation algorithm. This method has been verified with numerical examples of preventive maintenance (PM) using Monte Carlo simulation and was compared to the theoretical calculations. The results showed the prediction ability of the developed ANN model based on the theoretical calculations of estimating the reliability and the preventive maintenance cost of the component.

Chapter 6.

PROCESS DIAGNOSTICS AND PERFORMANCE MONITORING EXPLOITING ANN AND CUSUM CHANGE DETECTION ALGORITHM

6.1 Introduction

Manufacturing and energy sectors provide vast amounts of maintenance data and information that can be used proactively for performance monitoring and prognostic analysis, which lead to improved maintenance planning and scheduling activities. This leads to reduced unplanned shutdowns, maintenance costs and any fatal events that could affect the operations of the overall system. Performance and condition monitoring are among the most used strategies for prognostic and health management (PHM), in which different methods and techniques can be implemented to analyse maintenance and online data. Offshore wind turbines (WTs) are complex systems increasingly needing maintenance.

The costs of operating and maintaining wind turbines (WT) constantly need reduction as WT is one of the main electricity generation technologies and has the fastest growth rate in the world today [218]. Controlling the WT operations by having information about the changes in wind state and the turbine position could boost the efficiency of the generated power from WTs [31]. The potential failures of WTs depend on either the instantaneous instances or the age of the components and the associated failure rates. These failures cause system outages which have significant financial consequences [198]. A WT comprises several components: blades, rotor, yaw motor, tower, generator, controller, Nacelle, and gearbox [219]. The power generation capacity of WTs mostly depends on the gearbox which, together with the generator, makes up the drive train. Although the gearbox failure rates are typically low, they play a crucial role in WT operations. Therefore, malfunctions can result in significant downtime and expensive maintenance costs [220].

In condition-based maintenance (CBM) and predictive maintenance (PdM), condition monitoring systems play a crucial role in reducing the costs of occurred failures and enhancing the functionality of any system as they are being widely used as a tool for the detection of anomalies and failures by providing early warnings [30].

This chapter proposes a performance monitoring system of the WT gearbox efficiency based on the power generation process by exploiting artificial neural networks (ANN) composed of different network designs and training algorithms, along with the state change detection CUSUM algorithm.

6.2 Methodology

The proposed methodology for the performance monitoring process is depicted in **Figure 6.1**.

Figure 6.1. The proposed gearbox performance monitoring methodology

The main steps of the proposed methodology are the following:

1. Operational SCADA data acquisition: Simulated data are created for different gearbox efficiency levels of the same wind turbine (WT) type, as discussed in **section 2.3**.
2. Data pre-processing: The transient data are removed from the generated data sets.

3. ANN modelling: Two ANN models have been developed using different types of ANN training algorithms and structures to predict the gearbox efficiency of the WT and the generated electrical power in different gearbox efficiency levels.
4. Power residuals are calculated based on the developed ANN model to be used in the monitoring process.
5. Monitoring process: The modelled power residuals are analysed using the CUSUM state change detection algorithm to monitor the WT gearbox performance in different efficiency levels and detect any deviations or abnormal states if they exist. In addition, the gearbox efficiency prediction assists in monitoring the gearbox itself, and it helps avoid severe failure that might be caused due to the decreasing of the gearbox efficiency below the manufacturer threshold.

6.3 Results and discussions

6.3.1 Power and gearbox efficiency – ANN prediction models development

The power measurements are normalised using the min-max normalisation process using Eq. (2.25).

Two ANN models were developed to predict the power: ANN-MLP and ANN-NBN. The datasets of the efficiency levels 1 and 3 (see **Figure 2.11**) were used to train and test the developed models with 80%-20% training and testing splitting ratio. While the dataset of the efficiency level 2 was used to validate the developed models. **Table 6.1** presents a summary of the two developed ANN models. The predicted power was modelled with respect to the wind speed and gearbox efficiency using the ANN architectures depicted in **Figure 6.2**.

Figure 6.2. ANN architectures for power predictions. A: 2 inputs, 1 output FCN; B: 2 inputs, 1 output MLP 2-2-1 (N is the neuron index)

Table 6.1. Summary of the ANN models developed for the prediction of the generated power and the gearbox efficiency

ANN model	Model I	Model II
Variable's normalisation	Min-max normalisation	
Architecture	MLP 2-2-1	FCN
No. neurons in the hidden layers	2	3
Hidden layers activation function	Hyperbolic tangent (tanh)	
Outputs activation function	Hyperbolic tangent (tanh)	
Training algorithm / computation method	LM – forward-backward	NBN – forward-backward
No. patterns / training (80%)	1600	
No. patterns / test (20%)	400	
Error function	Root mean squared error (RMSE)	

The same architecture of the two models explained above was also used to predict the gearbox efficiency utilising the datasets of the efficiency levels 1 and 3 for testing and training, while the dataset of the efficiency level 2 was used for validation. But in this case, the predicted gearbox efficiency was modelled with respect to wind speed and power using the two ANN architectures as depicted in

Figure 6.3.

Figure 6.3. ANN architectures for gearbox efficiency prediction. A: 2 inputs, 1 output FCN; B: 2 inputs, 1 output MLP 2-2-1 (N is the neuron index)

It is worth mentioning that the developed prediction models are solely based on the simulated datasets of the three efficiency levels of the WT type “DeWindD6 1250 kW” and can be generalised to other types of WTs in future works.

6.3.2 Evaluation, selection and validation of ANN-based prediction models

Table 6.2 shows the validation metrics based on the performance measure RMSE used for checking the prediction accuracy of the developed ANN models.

Table 6.2. Performance metrics using RMSE to evaluate the developed prediction models

ANN model	Power prediction models		Efficiency prediction model	
	Model I	Model II	Model I	Model II
Training RMSE - Normalised	0.0222	0.0191	0.0388	0.0359
Testing RMSE - Normalised	0.0219	0.0195	0.0396	0.0367
Validation RMSE - Normalised	0.0212	0.0198	0.0192	0.0230
Average RMSE -Normalised	0.0217	0.0194	0.0325	0.0318

It can be seen that all models have a relatively small RMSE; training, testing and validation RMSE values are close to each other. The least RMSE means better prediction performance. Thus, the best RMSE value was achieved by model II (ANN-NBN) with slightly lower RMSE values than model I. Model II of power predictions was selected then to calculate the power residuals and monitor the performance of the WT power generation process.

The dataset of the efficiency level 2 was used for further validation of model II for both the prediction of power and gearbox efficiency. It is known that for the simulation of this dataset, the efficiency was set to 97%. During validation, the efficiency of this dataset was predicted at 96.4%, which can be considered a high prediction accuracy.

Regarding the prediction models, there were 12 estimated weights for each; eight input weights (IW) between the inputs and hidden layers and one layer weights (LW) between the hidden layers and the output. Two inputs and one output are included in each model. The biases are b_1 for the input layers and b_2 for the output layer. The weights are taken from the best-trained ANN models based on the lowest RMSE (Model II for both power and gearbox efficiency prediction).

Table 6.3 provides the estimated values of (b_1), (b_2), (IW) and (LW) from the best-trained ANN model used for power prediction. Similarly, Table 6.4 provides the same estimates from the best-trained ANN model developed for gearbox efficiency prediction.

Table 6.3. Weights and biases of the best-trained ANN power prediction model

b_1	b_2	IW			LW
17.09214	---	-18.95625	-6.37007	---	---
-0.36432	---	0.99391	-0.33618	-2.33843	---
---	3.37135	1.53391	0.15928	-2.73824	1.30765

Table 6.4. Weights and biases of the best-trained ANN gearbox efficiency prediction model

b_1	b_2	IW			LW
2.37085	---	-6.87395	-9.08612	---	---
-10.38677	---	0.12185	5.35551	-5.03385	---
---	-562.47041	26.5025	705.80450	147.0163	-493.26603

6.3.3 Importance analysis

The influence of each input variable of the developed best performance ANN models for both power and gearbox efficiency prediction were analysed using the predictors' importance analysis to order the variable predictors according to their respective "importance". Knowing that, the importance analysis is a specific type of sensitivity analysis that focuses on identifying the most important inputs regarding their impact on the outputs. The importance analysis was performed using SPSS software based on the combined training and testing samples.

Table 6.5 and **Figure 6.4** show that the most significant input feature is wind speed for the power prediction model, with around 97%, while the gearbox efficiency has the lowest effect, with only 3%; this refers to the fact that the gearbox efficiency is decreasing over a long time, unlike the short time wind speed variations. Despite the minor importance of gearbox efficiency, it can affect the power production process over the long terms. Similarly, both power and wind speed are influential input features with respect to gearbox efficiency prediction, with 54% and 46%, respectively.

Table 6.5. Importance analysis of input features of the developed models

Power prediction ANN model II				Gearbox efficiency prediction ANN model II		
Input feature	Variable Rank %	Importance	Order	Variable Rank %	Importance	Order
Wind speed	97	0.971	1	54	0.541	1
Power		--		46	0.459	2
Gearbox efficiency	3	0.029	2		--	

Figure 6.4. Importance analysis results of different input features; left figure: for power prediction, right figure: for gearbox efficiency prediction

In practice, the gearbox efficiency is also an influential input in terms of power prediction; the decreased level of gearbox efficiency causes a decrement in the generated power in a manner that the power curve is shifted downwards.

6.3.4 Power residuals calculation

The term “power residual” refers to the difference between the measured power of the different efficiency levels and the predicted power of the reference efficiency (100%) level based on the best-trained ANN power prediction model, as Eq. (6.1).

$$\text{Power residual } (r_{(i)}) = \text{Power_measured}(i) - \text{Power_predicted}(i) \quad (6.1)$$

Some statistical descriptors of the power residuals based on the predictions by the ANN model II is presented in **Table 6.6**.

Table 6.6. Statistical descriptors of the calculated power residuals of each efficiency level (kW)

Efficiency level	Mean	Standard deviation	Variance	Range	Min	Max
1	1.078	22.498	506.164	144.217	-59.175	85.043
2	-2.403	23.390	547.085	146.479	-70.241	76.239
3	-2.110	22.881	523.526	147.682	-77.040	70.642

A sample of the normalised measured and predicted power and their calculated residuals are presented in **Figure 6.5**.

Figure 6.5. Sample of the normalised measured power and predicted power by ANN model II (above) and their residuals (below)

It can be noticed from **Figure 6.5** and **Table 6.2** that the prediction error (RMSE) is relatively small for the power prediction model; the training and testing RMSEs are relatively close to each other.

From **Table 6.6** and **Figure 6.5**, it can be observed that the values of the power residuals of the efficiency levels resulting from the ANN model predictions have significant variations. Thus, the mean of each efficiency level indicated that all residuals are shifted toward the negative side due to the increased degradation in the gearbox.

6.3.5 Performance monitoring of the gearbox using CUSUM change detection algorithm

The cumulative summation (CUSUM) algorithm is usually utilised for state change detection and gearbox performance monitoring; it is known for its robustness to detect small changes in the mean of time series that is stationary between two changepoints.

The ANN-NBN model II of the power prediction, as shown in **Table 6.2**, has a relatively small error. The power prediction model II and its related power residuals can be used as a baseline for the monitoring process. Once the WT is operating as the baseline (normal state), the model can provide accurate power output predictions along with minor power residuals between the measured and

the predicted power. When the WT has abnormal operating conditions (e.g., decreased gearbox efficiency), the output variables deviate from the baseline model, and then the model produces increasingly shifted predicted power residuals. Using the ANN model II as a baseline, the gearbox efficiency is monitored based on the produced power in each efficiency level. The monitoring process aims at detecting any abnormal state change related to the power residuals due to the decreasing gearbox efficiency. The CUSUM change detection algorithm test is performed for that purpose, as shown in **Figure 6.6**.

Figure 6.6. CUSUM change detection algorithm flow chart

The main goal of the CUSUM test is to compare two hypotheses \mathcal{H}_0 and \mathcal{H}_1 , which represent the normal and abnormal states of the different efficiency levels, respectively, to see which one best fits the given datasets.

A scalar set of the ANN predicted power residuals $r(i) = \{r(1), r(2) \dots r(k)\}$ is used as input. Assuming that the power residuals have Gaussian (normal) distribution, then the hypotheses are as follows:

$\mathcal{H}_0: r(i) \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_0, \sigma^2)$ for $i = (1, \dots, k)$ (The mean of normal state has no changes)

$\mathcal{H}_1: r(i) \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_0, \sigma^2)$ for $i = (1, \dots, k_0)$, $r(i) \sim \mathcal{N}(\mu_1, \sigma^2)$ for $i = (k_0, \dots, k)$ (The mean of the normal state changed at k_0)

Where:

k_0 is the unknown change time. μ_0 and μ_1 are the means of the ANN power residuals before and after the potential change, respectively. k is the number of total measuring points. σ is the standard deviation of the normal state.

The corresponding log-likelihood ratio $s(i)$ for detecting a change in the mean of the ANN power residuals from μ_0 (normal state – efficiency level 1) and μ_1 (abnormal state – efficiency levels 2 and 3) can be obtained with Eq. (6.2) [140].

$$s(i) = \frac{\mu_1 - \mu_0}{\sigma^2} \left(r(i) - \frac{\mu_1 + \mu_0}{2} \right) \quad (6.2)$$

The recursive form of the CUSUM algorithm is an efficient method for performing the CUSUM test. The recursive form of the decision function is calculated as Eq. (6.3).

The behaviour of the log-likelihood ratio $s(i)$ has a negative drift before the change resulting from the degradation in the gearbox efficiency, and then it has a positive drift after the change along with the change occurrence time \hat{k}_0 and the stopping time k_a , as can be seen in **Figure 6.7**.

Figure 6.7. Change indicator of the log-likelihood ratio of the ANN power residuals

$$g(k) = \max(0; g(k-1) + s(k)) \quad (6.3)$$

The alarm function is presented in Eq. (5.42).

$$d(k) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } g(k) > h \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (6.4)$$

A user-defined threshold h is used to make a reasonable balance between a quick-change detection and a low false alarm rate. h is always positive; only the contributions to the cumulative sum that add up to a positive number must be considered to determine the decision function [221].

To avoid or reduce the false alarms and missed change detections caused by the parameter variations, the h must consider the maximum magnitudes of residuals under the normal state of the efficiency level, and then the threshold can be calculated as Eq. (6.5).

$$h = 1.5 \times \{\max g(k): k < k_a\} \quad (6.5)$$

The stopping time k_a , which can be called alarm time as well, is the time instant at which $g(k)$ crosses the h .

$$k_a = \min\{k: g(k) \geq h\} \quad (6.6)$$

The change occurrence time k_0 can be estimated as the time instant \hat{k}_0 at which $s(k)$ changes from negative to positive slope as indicated by Eq. (6.7).

$$\hat{k}_0 = k_a - N(k_a) \quad (6.7)$$

$N(k)$ is the number of successive observations in which the decision function remains positive, as expressed in Eq. (6.8).

$$N(k) = N(k-1)1_{\{g(k-1)>0\}} + 1 \quad (6.8)$$

where $1_{\{g(k-1)>0\}}$ is the indicator of event $g(k-1) > 0$, namely, $1_{\{g(k-1)>0\}} = 1$ when $g(k-1) > 0$ is true, otherwise $1_{\{g(k-1)>0\}} = 0$.

Figure 6.8 shows the recursive CUSUM decision function of the ANN power residuals of the three efficiency levels, in which the first efficiency level is considered normal and the others abnormal states in terms of the degraded gearbox efficiency. The upper chart presents the recursive CUSUM without re-initialisation, where $h = 3.459$. While the lower chart presents the recursive CUSUM with re-initialisation once h is crossed ($g(k) > h$). The stopping time (alarm) $k_a=1018$ is also shown there.

Figure 6.8. Recursive CUSUM decision function: without re-initialisation (upper chart) and with re-initialisation (lower chart)

As depicted in **Figure 6.8** (upper chart), during the state change occurrence, the CUSUM of $(g(k))$ starts increasing. Larger degradation indicates a higher slope. On the other hand, it can be seen in **Figure 6.8** (lower chart) that the first stopping alarm is triggered when the first state change is detected by the CUSUM; the other alarms indicate the decreasing in the gearbox efficiency as the CUSUM increases, as shown in **Figure 6.8** (upper chart).

The threshold h was selected to avoid false alarms. However, a change detection time delay D might occur accordingly, as seen in Eq. (6.9). Thus, there is a trade-off between false alarms and detection time.

$$D = k_a - k \quad (6.9)$$

Table 6.7 below summarises the performance monitoring results of the evaluated ANN power residuals of the three efficiency levels.

Table 6.7. Parameters description and performance monitoring results based on the CUSUM algorithm

Parameter	Description	Value
μ_0	Normal state mean (efficiency level 1)	1.078
μ_1	Abnormal state mean (efficiency levels 2 and 3)	-2.263
σ^2	Normal state standard deviation	22.498
h	User-defined threshold (Eq. (6.5))	3.459
k_a	Stopping time (first alarm) (Eq. (6.6))	1018
\hat{k}_0	Change occurrence time (Eq. (6.7))	969
D	Change detection time delay (Eq. (6.9))	18

As indicated in the performance monitoring results, the first state change alarm k_a and the estimated state change occurrence time (early warning) \hat{k}_0 helps the maintenance expert to respond effectively and make decisions; accordingly, this helps in reducing the effects of unexpected shutdowns and maintenance costs as well. The monitoring results of the power prediction ANN model can be used as an efficient tool to monitor the performance of the WT by analysing the triggered alarms and the existing power residuals, which probably indicate abnormal variations of the WT performance based on the changes in the gearbox efficiency. Moreover, the monitoring results can be used for further analysis, such as fault detection and prediction. On the other hand, the results of the gearbox efficiency prediction ANN model can be used in two ways. First, comparing the predicted gearbox efficiency of a specific time frame with a threshold provided by the manufacturer to monitor the efficiency degradation over time. Secondly, the remaining useful life of the gearbox based on its efficiency over several time cycles can be estimated based on the predicted and expected efficiencies and the efficiency threshold provided by the manufacturer. This helps in performing better maintenance plans and schedules.

6.4 Summary

Performance monitoring of the gearbox is based on different efficiency levels of the same type of wind turbine. The degradation models were developed based on the generated active power resulting from different efficiency levels of the gearbox, which is a critical component of the WTs. The levels of the gearbox efficiency over time are monitored in terms of the resulting power residuals and are modelled using ANN with a unique network architecture. The monitoring process uses the recursive form of the cumulative summation (CUSUM) change detection algorithm to detect the state change point where the gearbox efficiency is decreased by evaluating the power residuals predicted by the ANN model. To increase the monitoring effectiveness, a second ANN model was developed to predict the gearbox efficiency for monitoring any failure that could happen once the gearbox efficiency decreased below a threshold.

Chapter 7.

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

7.1 Conclusions

Different novel data-driven (ML)-based models for fault prognostics, degradation prediction and performance monitoring of mechanical components were developed to assist in achieving better technical efficiency of the maintenance system in an Industry 4.0 environment. The developed models were presented and analysed in this dissertation, from which the following overall conclusions can be drawn:

- The proposed improved NBN training algorithm with the extended accumulative step in the network design achieved highly accurate predictions and increased the prognostic model's ability to maintain the monotony of the increasing degradation path of the mechanical component with lower related prediction errors and higher prediction success rate. Moreover, the used data filtering process, along with the FCN and ACN architectures, reduced the number of the required neurons in the network, required less training time, and consumed less memory. Moreover, the used feed-forward-only computations decreased the number of required operations during the training process. The FCN and ACN architectures provide efficient training but require more complex computations.
- The novel fault prognostics method based on the improved accumulative ANN-NBN enabled highly accurate failure and RUL predictions of mechanical components. Moreover, it effectively allows us to model the failure behaviour of arbitrarily failed machine components and deal with complex mechanical systems (consisting of several independent machines). RUL estimates can be integrated into real-time monitoring systems' dashboards providing scheduling alerts or failure alarms to make the maintenance team able to respond to changes in machines' health promptly and without affecting other operations.
- The investigation, performance evaluation, prediction ability and comparative analysis between the different ML-based fault prognostics models, including different network architectures, training algorithms, number of neurons and hidden layers, computation methods and transfer function types showed that the NBN training algorithm, over the other training algorithms, can train unique neural network architectures such as FCN and ACN. The improved accumulative ANN-NBN model achieved the best prediction success rate and

very small prediction error among the investigated models. Moreover, the improved accumulative ANN-NBN model effectively dealt with multiple mechanical components of different degradation laws.

- A probabilistic based-ANN prediction methodology of mechanical component's life degradation has been developed in a joint research project. The predictions included reliability estimation of successive degradation points. Moreover, the developed methodology has the ability to predict such lifetime indices for different degradation cycles following perfect maintenance replacement strategy. The ANN model was built based on a unique structure including the NBN training algorithm and the FCN architecture. The distribution parameters estimation of the successive degradation points was determined using the MLE method. Within this PhD research, this methodology has been tested and verified. The results showed high accuracy and ability to predict the distribution parameters of the degradation. The developed methodology was verified using a simulation of preventive maintenance cases. The simulation results of predicting failure time, estimating reliability and the distribution parameters confirms the probabilistic prediction ability of the developed methodology based on the theoretical calculations and its ability to deal with lifetime failure data of multiple degradation and replacement cycles (dynamic prediction).
- The main benefit of such a probabilistic degradation prediction method is that the reliability can be estimated at any time. Thus, no need to wait until the failure occurrence to analyse the degradation data and diagnose the component's state; such results can be used to assist in maintenance planning and scheduling and other prognostic models, e.g., PdM models, to estimate the RUL or other conditions of the component.
- To monitor the performance of a degraded mechanical component such as the gearbox of WT, two ANN models were developed with different network architectures, designs and training algorithms. The results showed the ability of these models to predict the output of the WT based on the decreased efficiency of the gearbox (generated power), moreover, to predict the gearbox efficiency based on the input wind speed and generated power. For performance monitoring, the power residuals were calculated from the best-trained power prediction ANN model. A methodology of power residuals prediction combined with a CUSUM change detection algorithm was proposed, analysed and presented to monitor the change of the WT's state. Combined with the developed ANN models, the recursive form of CUSUM

algorithm demonstrated an efficient way to monitor the performance of the WT and assist in detecting the gearbox efficiency decreasing and changes for better maintenance actions. The results show that the proposed method is efficient and accurate in monitoring and detecting the state changes of the different efficiency levels.

7.2 Future work

Through the research conducted in this dissertation, several related future research opportunities have been identified as the following:

- Regarding the novel fault prognostics method and the improved accumulative ANN-NBN: Future work can include a thorough comparative analysis between the developed accumulative ANN-NBN model and other types of physics-driven and hybrid methods. Other types of data, i.e., run-to-failure and multiple failure thresholds, could be used in the future. Other features of the maintenance data can be used, if available, to improve the model, such as vibration, noise, wear, and other features that could affect the lifespan of the machine components.
- The probabilistic ANN-NBN method: Future work to improve the developed methodology to handle multiple mechanical components with different degradation laws and/or different failure thresholds.
- Regarding the WT gearbox performance monitoring method: Future research could be carried out on utilising the used models and tools for developing failure detection, prediction and identification models using other appropriate types of real SCADA data towards the implementation of the PdM strategy. Additionally, the output of the monitoring process can be used for failure classification problems.
- In general, the proposed prediction methodologies can be used as a baseline to develop a comprehensive prognostic maintenance strategy such as predictive maintenance (PdM), including a health monitoring and prognosis system, failure detection, failure prediction, failure isolation and failure identification algorithms to boost the maintenance support system as a main requirement of integration in Industry 4.0 environment. The overall developed methodology and the results of the predicted failure and RUL could be used as a baseline to develop a comprehensive prognostic maintenance strategy, such as PdM.
- The proposed methodologies can be applied, and their applicability can be investigated in other applications of mechanical systems, such as the

mechanical components of energy, manufacturing, electrical, chemical, and automotive industries.

- Although the developed methods have shown their effectiveness through simulated data, further validations on real industrial data of different industrial applications in the scope of mechanical components can be considered a future opportunity to establish an integrated PdM strategy.

Chapter 8.

SCIENTIFIC CONTRIBUTION AND RELATED PUBLICATIONS

8.1 Scientific Contribution

Figure 8.1 presents the overall framework of the dissertation. Five theses, indicated by stars in Figure 8.1, have been derived from the research results.

Figure 8.1. Overall framework of the dissertation

8.1.1 Thesis 1:

An artificial neural network (ANN) composed of either a fully connected network or arbitrarily connected network architecture trained by the neuron-by-neuron training method and an accumulative step can model the multi-cycle degradation process of mechanical components with a few number of neurons. In the accumulative step, the actual output of the ANN in the last layer is added to its previous output; this solution maintains the monotonously increasing natural trend of the degradation process during the training. The model outperforms other machine learning models such as Random Forest, Support Vector Machines, non-linear regression (logistic) and Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) in terms of the achieved error using the simulated degradation data.

Publications related to this thesis: [P1].

8.1.2 Thesis 2:

In the case of mechanical components with multiple degradation cycles that follow a perfect maintenance replacement strategy, a new data-driven fault prognostics method has been built from an artificial neural network composed of a fully connected network architecture of 3 neurons and an accumulative step, using the neuron-by-neuron training algorithm along with forward-only computations. In the case of the applied simulated degradation datasets, the method can efficiently predict the failures and estimate the best possible remaining useful life of mechanical components having different degradation laws with a high prediction success rate (100%) and a small error (0.0072 RMSE). In the case of real degradation data, the method outperforms published similar prediction models in terms of the achieved error (0.05176 RMSE) when predicting the flank wear of the cutting tool obtained from the NASA Ames milling dataset and using the machining time, depth of cut, feed rate and material type as inputs.

Publications related to this thesis: [P1], [P2], [P3], [P4].

8.1.3 Thesis 3:

In the case of the applied simulated degradation datasets, the neuron-by-neuron (NBN) training algorithm can efficiently train artificial neural networks with fully connected network (FCN) and arbitrarily connected network (ACN) architectures to predict the multi-cycles degradation path of a mechanical component using the main parameters showed in the table below for the best-trained prediction models.

Network Architecture	FCN	ACN
Number of neurons	8	3
Computation method	NBN-forward backward	
Hidden layers activation function	Hyperbolic tangent (tanh)	
Output activation function	linear	
RMSE	0.00077	0.00063

The prediction using the FCN architecture achieves a better average prediction success rate of 97.2% and an average error of 0.00065 RMSE compared to the multi-layer-perceptron architecture, which achieves an average prediction success rate of 77.6% and an average error of 0.02488 RMSE.

Publications related to this thesis: [P1], [P3], [P5].

8.1.4 Thesis 4:

A new general data-driven prediction toolset has been developed in a joint research project to probabilistically predict the successive values of the multi-cycle degradation process of a mechanical component following a perfect maintenance replacement strategy. This toolset is composed of an artificial neural network having a fully connected network or arbitrarily connected network architecture, having one input for the time steps, as many outputs as the number of the distribution parameters, and extra inputs of the preceding predictions; it uses the Maximum likelihood estimation method to estimate the distribution parameters, the neuron-by-neuron training algorithm to calculate the gradient efficiently along with the Broyden-Fletcher-Goldfarb-Shanno optimisation algorithm to minimise the negative log-likelihood.

A new specific data-driven prediction tool derived from the general toolset can predict the distribution parameters (mean and variance) of the assumed normal distribution function of the degradation, which are used for failure prediction within a preventive maintenance optimisation algorithm. This prediction tool is

composed of a fully connected network architecture with four neurons in two hidden layers and two neurons in the output layer for the two distribution parameters, having one input for the timesteps and two inputs for two preceding predictions. The integrated algorithm of this prediction tool and a Monte Carlo simulation-based optimisation tool can find the optimal preventive maintenance time along with minimising the cost per unit time, where the failure probability is predicted. In the case of the simulated multi-cycle degradation data, the tool finds the expected value of the optimal preventive maintenance time with a small relative error (0,82%) compared to the theoretical calculations.

8.1.5 Thesis 5:

In the case of the applied wind turbine simulated data, artificial neural networks can successfully predict the generated electrical power and the gearbox efficiency by exploiting the neuron-by-neuron (NBN) training algorithm with forward-backward computations and fully connected network (FCN) architecture of 3 neurons. The best-trained model can achieve an average error of 0.01940 RMSE in the case of power prediction and 0.03180 RMSE in the case of gearbox efficiency prediction.

The power residuals of the best-trained power prediction model can be evaluated using a proper change detection algorithm to monitor the performance of the gearbox and detect any deviations or changes in the gearbox efficiency.

Publications related to this thesis: [P2], [P5], [P6], [P7].

8.2 List of publications

8.2.1 Publications related to the theses

- [P1] **B. Shaheen**, Á. Kocsis, and I. Németh, “Data-driven failure prediction and RUL estimation of mechanical components using accumulative artificial neural networks,” *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 119, no. December 2022, p. 105749, Mar. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.engappai.2022.105749.
- [P2] **B. W. Shaheen** and I. Németh, “Integration of Maintenance Management System Functions with Industry 4.0 Technologies and Features—A Review,” *Processes*, vol. 10, no. 11, p. 2173, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.3390/pr10112173.
- [P3] **B. Shaheen**, I. Németh, and Á. Kocsis, “Comparison of Artificial Neural Network Technique-Based Failure Predictions of Mechanical Components,” in *The 6th International Conference on System Reliability and Safety (ICSRS)*, Nov. 2022, pp. 94–98, doi: 10.1109/ICSRS56243.2022.10067554.
- [P4] **B. W. Shaheen** and I. Németh, “Opportunistic Maintenance in the Digital Era : Resolving Conflict Between Managerial and Technological Objectives,” *The 9th Interdisciplinary Doctoral Conference (IDK2020)*, 2020.
- [P5] **B. Shaheen** and I. Németh, “Machine Learning Approach for Degradation Path Prediction Using Different Models and Architectures of Artificial Neural Networks,” *Periodica Polytechnica Mechanical Engineering*, vol. 66, no. 3, pp. 244–252, 2022, doi: 10.3311/ppme.20145.
- [P6] **B. W. Shaheen**, A. A. Hanieh, and I. Németh, “Fault detection of a wind turbine’s gearbox, based on power curve modeling and an on-line statistical change detection algorithm,” *Acta Polytechnica Hungarica*, vol. 18, no. 6, pp. 175–196, 2021, doi: 10.12700/APH.18.6.2021.6.10.
- [P7] **B. W. Shaheen** and I. Németh, “Performance Monitoring of Wind Turbines Gearbox Utilising Artificial Neural Networks — Steps toward Successful Implementation of Predictive Maintenance Strategy,” *Processes*, vol. 11, no. 1, p. 269, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.3390/pr11010269.

8.2.2 Other publications

- [P8] I. Németh, Á. Kocsis, D. Takács, **B. W. Shaheen**, M. Takács, A. Merlo, A. Eytan, L. Bidoggia, and P. Olocco, “Maintenance schedule optimisation for manufacturing systems,” *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, vol. 53, no. 3, pp. 319–324, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.ifacol.2020.11.051.
- [P9] T. Haddad, **B. W. Shaheen**, and I. Németh, “Improving Overall Equipment Effectiveness (OEE) of Extrusion Machine Using Lean Manufacturing Approach,” *Manufacturing Technology*, vol. 21, no. 1, pp. 56–64, 2021, doi: 10.21062/mft.2021.006.

APPENDIX

Through a joint research work in the Department of Manufacturing Science and Engineering at the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering - Budapest University of Technology and Economics (BME), through the National Laboratory of Artificial Intelligence project (MILab) a probabilistic ANN model was developed to predict the life degradation of mechanical components following perfect maintenance replacement strategy, and to estimate the reliability of the components over different time horizons.

The three researchers involved in this work are (Basheer Shaheen, István Németh, and Ádám Kocsis).

All results presented in chapter 5 are independent work of the PhD candidate Basheer Shaheen.

This model is described below in detail.

Maximum likelihood estimation

The probability density function (PDF) of a distribution is a function of y_1, \dots, y_n with fixed parameters $\theta = [\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_k]^T$. The PDF for each individual y_i can be written as Eq. (1).

$$P(y_1, \dots, y_n | \theta) = \prod_{i=1}^n P(y_i | \theta) \quad (1)$$

PDF is used to find the probability of sample-taking values when y_1, \dots, y_n are unknown and θ is known. The likelihood function does the same but in the opposite way: it considers that y_1, \dots, y_n values are constant and θ is a vector of the unknown independent parameters.

The likelihood function of θ can be described as Eq. (2).

$$L(y_1, \dots, y_n | \theta) = P(y_1, \dots, y_n | \theta) \quad (2)$$

In most cases, maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) is the most robust form of parameter estimation, which can be used for few to many samples and can handle heavily censored data better than regression [222]. The idea behind the method is that we are looking for the parameter(s) for which the probability of the samples coming from the distribution is the highest.

In statistical interference, to fit a distribution to data, the likelihood function is commonly used under the following assumptions: we have observed (i.e., failure) data y_1, \dots, y_n , unknown θ (distribution parameters) and the likelihood is calculated as Eq. (2).

Then, the maximum likelihood estimates of θ are θ_{MLE} that present the values that maximise the likelihood $L(y_1, \dots, y_n | \theta)$, as written in Eq. (3).

$$\theta_{\text{MLE}} = \arg \max_{\theta} L(y_1, \dots, y_n | \theta) \quad (3)$$

Maximising the likelihood is equivalent to maximising the log-likelihood $\log L(y_1, \dots, y_n | \theta)$, because the log function increases with its argument and changes the product of Eq. (1) into a sum as Eq. (4).

$$\theta_{\text{MLE}} = \arg \max_{\theta} \sum_{i=1}^n \log L(y_i | \theta) \quad (4)$$

Furthermore, the maximisation of the objective function of the likelihood is equivalent to the minimisation of the objective function of the negative log-likelihood, then:

$$\theta_{\text{MLE}} = \arg \min_{\theta} \Lambda(y_1, \dots, y_n | \theta) \quad (5)$$

Where the negative log-likelihood (Λ) is defined as Eq. (6).

$$\Lambda(y_1, \dots, y_n | \theta) = - \sum_{i=1}^n \log L(y_i | \theta) \quad (6)$$

Maximum likelihood optimisation algorithm

Different optimisation algorithms can be used to find the extremum of the likelihood function, such as line search methods, trust-region methods and Hessian approximation methods. BFGS (Broyden, Fletcher, Goldfarb, Shanno) is the most commonly used algorithm for Hessian approximation; it is also widely used in numerical optimisation and fitting ML algorithms [223].

The optimisation problem can be expressed as an unconstrained non-linear optimisation task as Eq. (5). In this research, the BFGS optimisation algorithm was used to minimise the negative log-likelihood (Λ).

BFGS is a second-order algorithm that belongs to part of a class of algorithms known as Quasi-Newton Methods, which are extensions to Newton's Method that utilises the Hessian matrix. Quasi-Newton methods approximate the inverse of the Hessian matrix using the gradient; thus, the Hessian and its inverse do not need to be determined exactly for each step of the algorithm [223] [224].

For the mathematical formulations, we use \mathbf{w} instead of θ , $\mathbf{w} = \theta$, to follow the traditional notations of the ANNs. For the Quasi-Newton direction, we have;

$$\Delta \mathbf{w}_k = -H_k^{-1} \nabla \Lambda(\mathbf{w}_k) \quad (7)$$

Where, \mathbf{w}_k is a vector of the estimated parameters of $k = 1, 2, \dots, i$ iteration, H_k^{-1} is the approximation of the inverse Hessian at \mathbf{w}_k and $\nabla \Lambda(\mathbf{w}_k)$ is the gradient of the objective function.

The inverse Hessian can then be used to determine the direction to move in using quasi-Newton techniques like BFGS, but the step size is no longer known. In order to determine how far to move in the chosen direction, the BFGS algorithm uses a line search in that direction. The complete derivation of the BFGS optimisation algorithm can be found in [222], [223], [224].

The inverse update of the Hessian matrix H_k is used in the algorithm as the first step as Eq. (8).

$$H_{k+1}^{-1} = \left(I - \frac{\mathbf{s}_k \mathbf{y}_k^T}{\mathbf{y}_k^T \mathbf{s}_k} \right) H_k^{-1} \left(I - \frac{\mathbf{y}_k \mathbf{s}_k^T}{\mathbf{y}_k^T \mathbf{s}_k} \right) + \frac{\mathbf{s}_k \mathbf{s}_k^T}{\mathbf{y}_k^T \mathbf{s}_k} \quad (8)$$

Where I is the initialised value of H , \mathbf{s}_k is the step where $\mathbf{s}_k = \alpha_k \mathbf{p}_k$ and $\mathbf{w}_{k+1} = \mathbf{w}_k + \mathbf{s}_k$, and $\mathbf{y}_k = \nabla \Lambda(\mathbf{w}_{k+1}) - \nabla \Lambda(\mathbf{w}_k)$. Moreover, α_k is the position step length, and the search direction $\mathbf{p}_k = -H_k \nabla \Lambda(\mathbf{w}_k)$.

Eq. (8) can be computed efficiently without temporary matrices, recognising that H_k^{-1} is symmetric, and $\mathbf{y}_k^T H_k^{-1} \mathbf{y}_k$ and $\mathbf{s}_k^T \mathbf{y}_k$ are scalars as in Eq. (5.43).

$$H_{k+1}^{-1} = H_k^{-1} + \frac{(\mathbf{s}_k^T \mathbf{y}_k + \mathbf{y}_k^T H_k^{-1} \mathbf{y}_k)(\mathbf{s}_k \mathbf{s}_k^T)}{(\mathbf{s}_k^T \mathbf{y}_k)^2} - \frac{H_k^{-1} \mathbf{y}_k \mathbf{s}_k^T + \mathbf{s}_k \mathbf{y}_k^T H_k^{-1}}{\mathbf{s}_k^T \mathbf{y}_k} \quad (9)$$

ANN model development

The MLE method was used to estimate the distribution parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ of the degradation data by selecting the weights of the ANN neurons \mathbf{w} , which maximise the likelihood or minimise the negative likelihood. In other words, the neural network is a function that associates a degradation data point with the distribution parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}$.

To calculate the network weights for each input datapoint $Xp(i)$, there is an ANN prediction $Yp(i)$ that is part of the distribution of the desired outputs $dp(i)$, as presented in [Figure 0.1](#) and Eq. (10).

$$Yp(i) = \text{ANN}(Xp(i), \mathbf{w}) \quad (10)$$

Figure 0.1. ANN input-output structure

Then, the training data is expressed as Eq. (11) for $i = 1, \dots, n$ where n is the number of internal and external inputs.

$$\text{Training data} = \{(Xp(1), dp(1)), \dots, (Xp(n), dp(n))\} \quad (11)$$

The weights of the trained ANN \mathbf{w} are those parameters ($\mathbf{w} = \boldsymbol{\theta}$) that minimise the negative log-likelihood (Λ) as Eq. (12).

$$\mathbf{w}_l = \arg \min_{\mathbf{w}} \left(- \sum_{i=1}^n \log L(y_i | \text{ANN}(x_i | \mathbf{w})) \right) \quad (12)$$

The NBN training algorithm was used to calculate the gradient, whereas the MLE method was used to estimate the weights. Compared to other training algorithms, the NBN algorithm has a number of advantages, including the ability to handle neural networks with arbitrary connections and feed forward-only computation, as well as the direct computation of quasi-Hessian matrices without the need to compute and store the Jacobian matrix. An improved version of NBN computations called “forward-only” is used through the training algorithm to increase the efficiency of the Jacobian matrix computations by removing the backpropagation process, which would otherwise have to be repeated for each output in case the network had multiple outputs [169], [175].

The activation function $f_j(\cdot)$ and the weighted input net_j of the j^{th} neuron can be used to calculate each neuron’s output (y_i), as below:

$$y_j = f_j(net_j) \quad (13)$$

The weighted input of the j^{th} neuron in the case of learning point p is expressed in the model using the following equation:

$$net_j = \sum_{i=1}^{\overline{IY(j)}} w_{Yp(j,i)} y_{IY(j,i)} + \sum_{i=1}^{\overline{IX(j)}} w_{Xp(j,i)} \begin{cases} d_{p-\Delta(i),IX(j,i)} & \text{if } i \leq no \\ x_{p-\Delta(i),IX(j,i)} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} + w_{Bp(j)} \quad (14)$$

where $w_{Yp(j,i)}$ is the weight of the j^{th} neuron for the i^{th} internal (from a previous neuron) input, $y_{IY(j,i)}$ is the i^{th} internal input of the j^{th} neuron, $\overline{IY(j)}$ is the number of internal inputs of the j^{th} neuron, $\overline{IX(j)}$ is the number of external inputs of the j^{th} neuron, $Yp(j,i)$ is the position of weight of the i^{th} internal input of the j^{th} neuron, $Xp(j,i)$ is the position of weight of the i^{th} external input of the j^{th} neuron, $Bp(j)$ is the position of the bias weight of the j^{th} neuron. The k^{th} output of the system is denoted by

$$Y_{p,k} = y_{p,k} \quad k \in o \quad (15)$$

Then, for the next training

$$net_j = \sum_{i=1}^{\overline{IY(j)}} w_{n+1Yp(j,i)} \times E(y_{p-\Delta(i),IY(1,i)}, y_{p-\Delta(i),IY(2,i)}) + \sum_{i=1}^{\overline{IX(j)}} w_{Xp(j,i)} \begin{cases} d_{p-\Delta(i),IX(j,i)} & \text{if } i \leq no \\ x_{p-\Delta(i),IX(j,i)} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} + w_{n+1Bp(j)} \quad (16)$$

Where o is the set of indices of the output neurons, the number of elements of o is no , and E is the expected value. In the learning process, the negative log-likelihood as Eq. (8) was minimised to approximate the Hessian matrix using the BFGS optimisation function using Eq. (7-9).

$$\Lambda = \sum_{p=1}^P \lambda_p \quad (17)$$

Where P is the total number of patterns and λ_p is the following function:

$$\lambda_p = -\log(\varphi(d_p, \mathbf{Y})) \quad (18)$$

where φ is an arbitrary probability density function with no number of parameters, i.e. $Y_1, Y_2 \dots Y_{no}$, \mathbf{g} is the gradient vector of Λ . The gradient vector can be calculated by:

$$\mathbf{g} = \left[\frac{\partial \Lambda}{\partial w_1} \quad \frac{\partial \Lambda}{\partial w_2} \quad \dots \quad \frac{\partial \Lambda}{\partial w_{nw}} \right] \quad (19)$$

Let us denote the partial derivative of Eq. (18) with respect to the k^{th} output of the neural network by the following expression:

$$\lambda'_{k,p} \equiv \frac{\partial \lambda_p}{\partial Y_k} \quad (20)$$

Using Eq. (20) the i^{th} element of \mathbf{g} can be calculated by the following expression:

$$\frac{\partial \Lambda}{\partial w_i} = \sum_{k=1}^{no} \sum_{p=1}^P \lambda'_{k,p} \frac{\partial Y_{k,p}}{\partial w_i} = \sum_{k=1}^{no} \sum_{p=1}^P \lambda'_{k,p} j_i \quad (21)$$

Where the values j_i can be calculated by:

$$j_{Yp(j,i)} = \delta_{o_k,j} y_{IY(j,i)} \quad (22)$$

$$j_{Xp(j,i)} = \delta_{o_k,j} \begin{cases} d_{pC(p)-\Delta(i)} & \text{if } i \leq no \\ x_{pC(p)-\Delta(i)} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (23)$$

$$j_{Bp(j)} = \delta_{o_k,j} \quad (24)$$

Where the δ parameter can be calculated by the following expressions:

$$\delta_{j,j} = f'_j(\text{net}_j) \quad (25)$$

$$\delta_{j,i} = \delta_{j,j} \sum_{k=i}^{j-1} \begin{cases} w_{wp(j,k)} \delta_{k,i} & wp(j,k) \neq 0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

The pseudo-code of the log-likelihood function calculations is presented in **Figure 0.2**.

```

 $\Lambda=0$ 
For p=1 to P
  For j=1 to n
    Calculate  $y_j$  %Eq. (13)
  Next i
   $\Lambda += \lambda(d_p, \{y_i \mid i \in o\})$  %Eq. (17)
Next p
Return  $\Lambda$ 

```

Figure 0.2 Pseudo-code - Calculation of the log-likelihood function

Similarly, the pseudo-code of the gradient of the log-likelihood function calculations is presented in **Figure 0.3**.

```

 $g=0$ 
For p=1 to P
  For j=1 to n
    Calculate  $net_j$  %Eq. (14)
    Calculate  $y_j$  %Eq. (15)
    For i = 1 to j-1
      Calculate  $\delta_{j,i}$  %Eq.(25)
    Next i
  Next j
  For k=1 to  $n_o$ 
    For j=1 to n
      For i = 1 to  $\overline{IY(j)}$ 
        Calculate  $j_{Yp(j,i)}$  %Eq. (22)
      Next i
      For i = 1 to  $\overline{IX(j)}$ 
        Calculate  $j_{Xp(j,i)}$  %Eq. (23)
      Next j
      Calculate  $j_{Bp(j,i)}$  %Eq. (24)
    Next i
    For i=1 to  $nW$ 
       $g_i += \lambda'(d_p, \{y_j \mid j \in o\})$  %Eq. (21)
    Next i
  Next k
Next p
Return  $g$ 

```

Figure 0.3.Pseudo-code - Calculation of the gradient of the log-likelihood function

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